

ICAENS 2023 PROGRAM

Session 1.1			10 JULY 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-1	09:00-09:10	Developing Web Services and Challenges	Faris Sattar Hadi	Iraq	Mail Submission 2
Y-2	09:10-09:20	Wastewater Management: Techniques and Strategies	Hadjer MEZAACHE and Yahia HAMMAR	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2
Y-3	09:20-09:30	Natural Frequency-based Structural Health Monitoring in 2D and 3D Structures	Amar Kahouadji, Samir Tiachacht, Mohand Slimani and Amar Behtani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3
Y-4	09:30-09:40	New Hybrid Conjugate Gradient Algorithm For Unconstrained Optimization	Choubeila Souli, Raouf Ziadi, Asma Maiza	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4
Y-5	09:40-09:50	Study of structural, electronic, magnetic, thermoelectric and optical properties of X ₂ YZ full-heuslers by Ab initio calculations	Rachid Masrouf	Rachid Masrouf	Submission 5
Y-6	09:50-10:00	Structural, electronic and magnetic properties of perovskite systems : First-principles predictions and Monte Carlo simulations	Rachid Masrouf	Rachid Masrouf	Submission 6
Y-7	10:00-10:10	Multiplicity Results For Fractional Elliptic Equation Involving Critical Exponent	Djamel Abid	Algeria	Submission 7
Y-8	10:10-10:20	Feature Extraction Based on Genetic Algorithm for Medical Image Classification	Berrimi Fella	Algeria	Submission 8
Y-9	10:20-10:30	Improvement of electrical and dielectric performance of PVC nanocomposites under different types of aging	Lakhdar Madani, Abdelkrim Zebar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9
Y-10	10:30-10:40	Green synthesis of ZnO, MnO ₂ and MgO nanoparticles: a comparative study of their photocatalytic activity towards water soluble toxic dyes	Mohamed AIT OUMERACI, Tarek BERRAMA, Hayet TIZI, Feriel SAHOUL, Yassine KADMI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, France	Submission 10

Session 1.2			10 JULY 2023 09:00 11:00		
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Y-11	09:00-09:10	Effect of particle size on ZnO nanoparticles' photocatalytic activity for oxidizing water	Mohamed AIT OUMERACI, Tarek BERRAMA, Hayet TIZI, Yassine KADMI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, France	Submission 11
Y-12	09:10-09:20	Extending The Product Integration Method	Raouia BEN DAHMANE, Khansa BEN DAHMANE and Hanane KABOUL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 13
Y-13	09:20-09:30	Risk management in E-government projects	Zeynab Muradkhanli, Leyla Muradkhanli and Mohammad ali AL Qudah	Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan	Submission 14
Y-14	09:30-09:40	Structural and electronic properties of MoS ₂ monolayer	LOUAFI Widad, REZOUALI Karim, LOUNIS Samir	Algeria, Algeria, Germany	Submission 15
Y-15	09:40-09:50	Intercalated clay as efficient adsorbent for Congo red from aqueous solutions	AMAR Amine, KHELIFA Mounir, Kheira MAROUF-KHELIFA, KHELIFA Amine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 16
Y-16	09:50-10:00	Phytohormones and their role in adaptation to salt stress	Basti Asadova	Azerbaijan	Submission 17
Y-17	10:00-10:10	Na-isocationic salts of wheat, barley, beans and peas effect on germination of plant seeds	Basti Asadova	Azerbaijan	Submission 18
Y-18	10:10-10:20	Identification of gypsum using steaming process (the northwest of Ouled Djellal city, Algeria)	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 19
Y-19	10:20-10:30	Prediagnosis of Building Pathology Associated with Underground Dissolution Pathology Part I: A Case Study in the Northwest of Ouled Djellal City, Algeria	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 20
Y-20	10:30-10:40	Prediagnosis of Building Pathology Associated with Underground Dissolution Pathology Part II: A Case Study in the Northwest of Ouled Djellal City, Algeria	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 21

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P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-21	10:00-10:10	Identification of Subsidence Hazard through Site Visits: A Case Study in the Northwest of Ouled Djellal City, Algeria	Farouk Rebiai, Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 22
Y-22	10:10-10:20	EXPONENTIAL STABILITY OF SWELLING POROUS WITH GURTIN-PIPKIN THERMOELASTICITY AND TIME-VARYING DELAY TERM	Widad Karek, Lamine Bouzettouta and Abdallah Lallouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 24
Y-23	10:20-10:30	Comparison of the metrological performances of two Benzophenone sensors	LAIEB Roumaissa, GHODBANE Ilhem and ZOUGAR Saïda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 25
Y-24	10:30-10:40	Optimization of Physico-Chemical Treatment of Wastewater by Coagulation/Flocculation Using Pine Cone Extract as a Natural Coagulant using Response Surface Methodology.	Ouiem Baatache, Kerroum Derbal, Abderrezzaq Benalia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 26
Y-25	10:40-10:50	Experimental investigation of the water bypass phenomenon in light oil reservoirs using a glass micromodel and sand cores with a hydrophobic material	Zakaria Adjou, Hamid Lebtahi, Djamilia Boufades and Dobbi Abdelmadjid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 27
Y-26	10:50-11:00	Stability result of solutions for a Transmission wave equation with internal neutral delay	Baibeche Sabah, Bouzettouta Lamine and Karek Chafia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 29
Y-27	11:00-11:10	Uniqueness and Stability Results of Fractional Differential Equations	Mohamed Helal	Algeria	Submission 30
Y-28	11:10-11:20	Food hygiene assessment in catering establishments in central Morocco	Rachid Amaïach, Sanae Lairini, Mouhcine Fadil, Moussa Benboubker, Rabia Bouslamti, Soukaina El Amrani, and Abdelhakim El Ouali Lalami	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 31
Y-29	11:20-11:30	Sensorial and organoleptiques characteristics of Mech-Degla date flour	MATALLAH Boudour, BENAÏSSA Yamina, ADDOU Samia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 34
Y-30	11:30-11:40	Study of the electrochemical properties of the electroactivity of the nanocomposite poly-methylthiophene and titanium dioxide synthesized by electrochemical process	SMANI Dounia, MAOUCHE Naima	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 35

Session 1.4			10 JULY 2023 10:00-12:00		
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Y-31	10:00-10:10	Data analysis and kinetic modeling of textile wastewater biosorption using agricultural waste	Benkouachi Oumnia Rayane, Bouguettoucha Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 36
Y-32	10:10-10:20	Focus on the characterization of the bioactive components of the Moroccan Allium Cepa.L	Maryam Hanif, Abdelhakim Boudboud, Hamid Mazouz, Hassan Hajjaj and Abdelhay El harrak	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 37
Y-33	10:20-10:30	Evaluation of the influence of crushed sand on the qualities of concrete sand	Oday Jaradat, Karima Gadri and Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 38
Y-34	10:30-10:40	Water Quality in the Lezha-Shengjini Coastline, Central Adriatic Sea, Albania	Esmeralda Halo, Aurel Nuro, Bledar Myrtaj, Jonida Tahiraj, Sonila Kane, Kujtim Dule, Eriola Sila, Elisabeta Peti	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 39
Y-35	10:40-10:50	Adsorption of Calcium Phosphate: From Environmental Nutrient Cycling to Biomaterials and Biotechnology"	BENBOUDA Mouna, BOUDEMAGH Djalila, CHEBLI Derradji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 40
Y-36	10:50-11:00	Effect of an insecticide (acetamiprid) on behavior, morphology and Histology of earthworms, Eudrillus eugeniae (Kinberg,1867)	Berrouk-Houda, Bendjebbar Roumaissa.	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 41
Y-37	11:00-11:10	Copepod parasites of the gills of Luciobarbus callensis (Valencienne ,1842) and Carassius carassius (Linnaeus, 1758) collected from Beni- Haroun Dam (Mila, Algeria).	Houda Berrouk, Khelifi Naima, Boualleg Chahainez	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 43
Y-38	11:10-11:20	Effect of cadmium nitrate and Mercure chloride and their mixture on Earthworms Aporrectodea trapezoides (Duges, 1828)	Berrouk-Houda, Necib Asma, Aoun Chaima, Guerfi Sameh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 44
Y-39	11:20-11:30	Study the Hygrothermal Aging of Thermoplastics Polymers/Nanoclay Nanocomposites	Benalia Kouini, Amina Hachaichi, Asma Nour El Houda Sid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 47
Y-40	11:30-11:40	Simulating a Multi-Strain SECRH Epidemic Model	Id ouaziz Saida, EL Khomssi Mohammed	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 49

Session 1.5			10 JULY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-41	11:00-11:10	Experimental study of the Ductility of High Performance Concrete Beams Containing Steel Fibres	Touhami Tahenni	Algeria	Submission 50
Y-42	11:11-11:20	Optimal placement of DWES -SVC in power system for voltage stability enhancement using CPF	Abdelkrim Zebar, Lakhdar Madani	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 52
Y-43	11:20-11:30	Development of an application used for calculation and estimation of solar radiation components at ground	Ilyas ROUGAB and Nabil ABOUCHABANA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 53
Y-44	11:30-11:40	DEGRADATION OF ORGANIC PHARMACEUTICAL POLLUTANTS DYE USING A BIO SYNTHESIZED NANOMATERIALS (TiO ₂)	Abouelkacem SAHRAOUI, Abennour ZERTAL	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 54
Y-45	11:40-11:50	Using artificial intelligence technology to improve education	Mudasir Ali Rind, Mohannad Ali AL-Qudah	Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan	Submission 55
Y-46	11:50-12:00	An Advanced Hybrid Salp Swarm Algorithm for Global Optimization Tasks	Nacer Meriem, Hamaizia Tayeb and Chabekh Meriem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 58
Y-47	12:00-12:10	Preparation and Characterization of hydrogel film by chemical encapsulation using HPMC for hydrophobic drug delivery.	BENNAADJA SOUHIB, SOLTANI EL KHAMSA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 59
Y-48	12:10-12:20	Oxide Coated Noble Metal Nanoparticles in Biosensors: Analytical Modeling and Discrete Dipole Approximation Method	Adil Bouhadiche and Soulef Benghorieb	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 61
Y-49	12:20-12:30	SYNTHESIS, ANTIPROLIFERATIVE EVALUATION AND DNA/RNA BINDING EXAMINATION OF PHENYLENE-BIS(BENZAZOLES)-SUBSTITUTED AMIDINOS	Nweje-Anyalowu Paul Chukwuemeka, Ihuomah Victor Emeka and Nweje-Anyalowu Kenneth Chisom	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 63
Y-50	12:30-12:40	Clay-based carrier for gastrointestinal drug release: investigation ibuprofen as a model drug	Benbekai Rima, Chebli Derradji and Bouguettoucha Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 64

Session 1.6			10 JULY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-51	11:00-11:10	Synthesis of modify zeolite from volcanic glass	Benbekai Rima, Chebli Derradji and Bouguettoucha Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 65
Y-52	11:11-11:20	EXISTENCE AND LOCATION OF NODAL SOLUTIONS FOR QUASILINEAR CONVECTION- ABSORPTION NEUMANN PROBLEMS	Abdelkader Benali	Algeria	Submission 67
Y-53	11:20-11:30	EXISTENCE AND LOCATION OF NODAL SOLUTIONS FOR QUASILINEAR CONVECTION- ABSORPTION NEUMANN PROBLEMS	Abdelkader Benali	Algeria	Submission 68
Y-54	11:30-11:40	MULTIPLICITY RESULTS OF NONLOCAL SINGULAR PDES WITH CRITICAL SOBOLEV-HARDY EXPONENT	Abdelkader Benali	Algeria	Submission 69
Y-55	11:40-11:50	A critical elliptic problem involving exponential and singular nonlinearities	Abdelkader Benali	Algeria	Submission 70
Y-56	11:50-12:00	Study of the effect of pH on the efficiency of the removal of a pharmaceutical product by Fenton oxidation in distilled water	Chergui Fadoua Nihad, Chebbi Meriem and Ounoki Samira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 71
Y-57	12:00-12:10	Kaolinite: a versatile with promising applications in modern pharmaceutical development	AMATA Rim, BOUNOUALA Mohamed, ALSAFASFEH Ashraf	Algeria, Algeria, Jordan	Submission 72
Y-58	12:10-12:20	Natural phosphate of Djabel Onk: Physicochemical and mineralogical study	AMATA Rim, BOUNOUALA Mohamed, ALSAFASFEH Ashraf	Algeria, Algeria, Jordan	Submission 73
Y-59	12:20-12:30	Optimization of storage in a photovoltaic system with hybrid storage : Battery/ supercapacitor	Basma BENBOUYA, Hocine CHEGHIB and Mokhtar TEKOUK	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 74
Y-60	12:30-12:40	A Feasibility Study of Self Cooled Passive Device	Jaswinder Singh Mehta, Rajesh Kumar	India, India	Submission 76

Session 1.7			10 JULY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-61	12:00-12:10	Analysis of Turbulent Channel Flow and Heat Transfer Characteristics using CFD	Anas Sofi, Narjisse Amahjour and Abderrahman El kharrim	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 80
Y-62	12:11-12:20	Geotechnical, thermal and Physicochemical Characterization of Moroccan Clay from Settata Area for Construction Applications	ABOULOIFA Walid, ETTAKI Mohammed, and HAYANI MOUNIR Sanaa	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 81
Y-63	12:20-12:30	On the Asymptotic Normality of the Tail Value at Risk	Nour Elhouda Guesmia	Algeria	Submission 83
Y-64	12:30-12:40	Estimating the Value at Risk for Incomplete Heavy-Tailed Data	Nour Elhouda Guesmia	Algeria	Submission 84
Y-65	12:40-12:50	Analysis of Distribution Network Operation Integrated of Renewable Distributed Generation	Abdelkader Boukaroura and Mohammed Amroune	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 85
Y-66	12:50-13:00	Study Of The Properties Of A Oxide Pérovsrites NdMnO3	Abdelkader BOUHENNA, Boualem Kada	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 86
Y-67	13:00-13:10	Caractérisation of the metals TCO for applications in photovoltaics and optoelectronics	Abdelkader BOUHENNA, Boualem Kada	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 87
Y-68	13:10-13:20	First principles of calculation of the electronic, structural and magnetic properties of the YbPtTi alloy	ADDOU Oussama, TOUIA Amina	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 88
Y-69	13:20-13:30	The influence of conventional sintering on the microstructure and electrical properties of ZnO-based varistor	Yousra Malaoui, Faiçal kharchouche	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 90
Y-70	13:30-13:40	Existence, uniqueness results for fractional system using topological degree method	Chaima Saadi, Meriem Bounib	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 93

Session 1.8			10 JULY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-71	12:00-12:10	Accurate Finite Volume Investigation of laminar flow in a two-dimensional filled with the hybrid nanofluid	Chaima Saadi, Meriem Bounib	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 94
Y-72	12:11-12:20	Numerical analysis of mixed convection in a driven cavity using the finite volume method	Chaima Saadi, Meriem Bounib	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 95
Y-73	12:20-12:30	Positive Periodic Solutions of a first order neutral delay differential equation	Lynda Mezghiche, Rabah Khemis and Ahlème Bouakkaz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 96
Y-74	12:30-12:40	Studies of polyaniline/ graphene oxide nanocomposites as highly selective gas sensor: density functional theory calculations	Abir Boubli	Algeria	Submission 98
Y-75	12:40-12:50	Study on the position of dependability in achieving systems performance industrial	Ammar Chakhrit, Mohammed Bougofa, Islam Hadj Mohamed Guetarni and Mohammed Chennoufi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 101
Y-76	12:50-13:00	Optical Properties and FTIR Studies of MnO ₂ Doped Graphene Nanoparticles by Simple electrodeposition Method	Assia Tounsi, Leila Lamiri, Ouafia Belgherbi, Noudjoud Houas, Farid HABELHAMES, Ahmed BAHLOUL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 102
Y-77	13:00-13:10	Electro-Synthesis, characterization and capacitive performance of FTO/Polybithiophene- Ag composite	Assia Tounsi, Leila Lamiri, Ouafia Belgherbi, Noudjoud Houas, Farid HABELHAMES, Ahmed BAHLOUL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 103
Y-78	13:10-13:20	Facile Synthesis of Ferns-Like PbTh-silver as Binder-Free Faradic Electrodes for Supercapacitors with Improved Electrochemical Properties	Assia Tounsi, Leila Lamiri, Ouafia Belgherbi, Noudjoud Houas, Farid HABELHAMES, Ahmed BAHLOUL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 104
Y-79	13:20-13:30	Experimental Investigation of Shear Connectors' Effect on the Mechanical Performance of Steel Tubes Filled with Slag Concrete	Naoual Handel, Farida Khammar and Sarah Djouimaa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 107
Y-80	13:30-13:40	Influence of the addition of glass scraps on the compaction of limestone	Idir AMARA, Omar BOUDLAL, Fadhila GHANEM and Fatah BOUFOUDI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 109

Session 1.9			10 JULY 2023 13:00-15:00		
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Y-81	13:00-13:10	Study of the bearing capacity of a mixture of limestone and glass debris in CBR tests	Idir AMARA, Omar BOUDDLAL, Fadhila GHANEM and Fatah BOUFOUDI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 111
Y-82	13:11-13:20	AB-INITIO STUDY OF STRUCTURAL, ELECTRONIC AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF RbFeO ₃ AND CsFeO ₃ MATERIALS	Ahmed Memdouh Younsi, Abdelaziz Rabehi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 112
Y-83	13:20-13:30	Geotechnics In The Field Of Construction And Public Works	Guendoud Malika, Melbouci Bachir and Benlala Abdel Hafid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 116
Y-84	13:30-13:40	The role of active learning in the development of creative thinking in biology lessons	Basti Asadova	Azerbaijan	Submission 117
Y-85	13:40-13:50	Petrosimonieta brachiatae and Suaedeta confusae formations distributed in the territory of Azerbaijan	Sanubar Aslanova	Azerbaijan	Submission 119
Y-86	13:50-14:00	Comparative study of two topical feet formulations contained some of natural products	Fouzia Benoudjit, Sarra Deraï, Hasna El Amrani and Fatma Stiti	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 121
Y-87	14:00-14:10	The Potential of rGO@ZnO Photocatalyst for the Degradation of Organic Pollutants in Water	Kamilia MADI, Derradji CHEBLI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 122
Y-88	14:10-14:20	Numerical Solutions for a Laminated Timoshenko beam with delay	Chabekh Meriem, Chougui Nadhir and Nacer Meriem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 123
Y-89	14:20-14:30	Studies on adsorption of Congo red from aqueous solutions onto intercalated clay	AMAR Amine, KHELIFA Mounir, Kheira MAROUF-KHELIFA, KHELIFA Amine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 124
Y-90	14:30-14:40	Modeling of an oil jet pumps group ground drive working process	Denys Panevnyk	Ukraine	Submission 125

Session 1.10			10 JULY 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-91	13:00-13:10	Study Of The Influence Of Temperature And Illumination On The Electrical Characteristics Of A Photovoltaic Module	Khammar farida, Handel Naoual and Djouimaa Sarah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 126
Y-92	13:11-13:20	Free online editors for computer graphics in Geology and Earth sciences	Yuriy Vikhot, Solomiia Kril and Ihor Bubniak	Ukraine, Ukraine, Ukraine	Submission 128
Y-93	13:20-13:30	Problems of Modeling the geophysical characteristics of the Earth's Climate	Yuriy Vikhot, Vitaly Fourman	Ukraine, Ukraine	Submission 132
Y-94	13:30-13:40	Efficient Removal of Organic Pollution from Illizi Groundwater using Acacia Gum Powder as a Natural Bio-Adsorbent	Rania Remmani, Rachid Makhloufi and Messaoud Roumani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 133
Y-95	13:40-13:50	Performance of modified montmorillonite nanomaterials for removal of methyl orange	Houria REZALA	Algeria	Submission 137
Y-96	13:50-14:00	Synthesis, characterization, and molecular docking of new Schiff base derivative of dehydroacetic acid	Tinhinane LOUAILECHE, Salima TABTI and Chaima MAOUCHE	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 138
Y-97	14:00-14:10	Magnetic, Structural and Luminescent Properties of Sr-Ni-Al ₂ O ₃ Thin Film Elaborated By Spray Pyrolysis Method	A.Ziouche, M.Mokhtari, A. Hammouda, N. Boucherou, A. Haddad, N. Jebari, M. Ajili, N. Kemoun, S.Alleg	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 139
Y-98	14:10-14:20	Experimental Analysis of Flow Induced Vibrations in Heat Exchanger Tube Bundles with P/D of 1.54 Subjected to Crossflow	Muhammad Moin Akhtar, Javaria Qadeer	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 141
Y-99	14:20-14:30	Comparative genomics of Sunflower MYB transcription factors involved in cuticular wax biosynthesis under drought stress	Mahmood-ur-Rahman, Hafiz Muhammad Ahmad	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 142
Y-100	14:30-14:40	Enhancing the mechanical and morphological behavior of LDPE/PP blends without and with compatibilizer	Walid BENAYACHE, Mohamed Tahar BENANIBA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 143

Session 1.11			10 JULY 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-101	14:00-14:10	Incorporation of graphene oxide on the structural and thermal properties of HDPE	Walid BENAYACHE, Mohamed Tahar BENANIBA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 144
Y-102	14:11-14:20	Assessment of the Physicochemical Quality of Water at the Koudiet Medouar Drinking Water Treatment Plant – Batna -Northeast Algeria: An Environmental Monitoring Study	Amina BADJI	Algeria	Submission 148
Y-103	14:20-14:30	Sustainable Power Quality Improvement using a Renewable Energy-Fed UPQC System	Abdelkader YOUSFI, Youcef BOT	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 149
Y-104	14:30-14:40	Degradation of Congo red with Activated Biomass	Benkouachi Oumnia Rayane, Bouguettoucha Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 151
Y-105	14:40-14:50	A comparative study of optimization algorithms for estimating the parameters of photovoltaic models	Naoual TIDJANI, Houria REZALA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 153
Y-106	14:50-15:00	STUDY OF NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE OF RUGRA- AN INDIGENOUS MUSHROOM OF JHARKHAND	Neha Rai	India	Submission 154
Y-107	15:00-15:10	Properties of Waste Brick Powder based Geopolymer Mortar	Mohammed Nadjib AZIEZ, Abderraouf ACHOUR, BENSANIA Abdellah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 155
Y-108	15:10-15:20	DESIGN OF TEMPERATURE REGULATOR OF A FISHPOND	Yusuf Bello Saleh	Nigeria	Submission 156
Y-109	15:20-15:30	Energy Efficiency in Building Based on the BIPV Panels System Used as a Double Skin Envelop in a Hot Arid Region	Marouane Samir Guedouh, Mohamed Amine Khadraoui, Kamal Youcef and Houssein Sami Belmahdi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 162
Y-110	15:30-15:40	The induction of hepatic oxidative stress in NMRI mice fed a high-fat diet	Amina ABDELLATIF, Djaafar Babaali, Nada SLAMA, Karima BAHRIA, George BIRKMA YER, Mustapha OUMOUNA, Karine BENACHOUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Austria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 163

Session 1.12			10 JULY 2023 14:00-16:00		
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Y-111	14:00-14:10	Study of hybrid passive-active micromixers under an acoustic field	Zahra Ghorbani Kharaji, Vali Kalantar and Morteza Bayare	Iran, Iran, Iran	Submission 164
Y-112	14:11-14:20	Assessment of long-term morphological changes and sediment dynamics in the Madjerda-Northeast Algeria	Amina BADJI	Algeria	Submission 166
Y-113	14:20-14:30	Extraction of Cellulose from Alfa: A Sustainable Approach for Biomaterial Production	Asiya Rezzouq, Souad Zyade and Omar Cherkaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 167
Y-114	14:30-14:40	Drought tolerance assessment and trait associations in two wheat accessions under varying water stress conditions	Victor O. Olumekun, Abiola T. Ajayi, Hassana T. Isa, Vincent A. Lawal and Tomiloba F. Ojo	Nideria, Nigeria, Nigeria, USA, Nigeria	Submission 186
Y-115	14:40-14:50	Seeds Treatment And Nanotechnology - Review	Soltane Sabrine, Benmeddour Tarek	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 187
Y-116	14:50-15:00	Synthesis and characterization of MgZnCo Ternary Mixed Metal Oxide by the Sonochemical Method for Solid Hydrogen Storage	Safia HARRAT, Mounir SAHLI, Abdelhakim SETTAR, Khaled CHETHOUNA	Algeria, Algeria, France, France	Submission 190
Y-117	15:00-15:10	“Impact of Authentic Leadership Traits in Engineering Sector using MCDM”	Muhammad Junaid, Muhammad Sajid and Iqra Saeed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 193
Y-118	15:10-15:20	Artificial Neural Networks for seismic demand prediction of a single degree of freedom	BENBOKHARI Abdellatif, BENAZOUZ Chikh and MEBARKI Ahmed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 197
Y-119	15:20-15:30	Numerical Study: Comparison of Paraffin Deposition In The Laminar And Turbulent Regime	Oussama Benhacene, Rachid Boucetta	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 222
Y-120	15:30-15:40	A Comparative Analysis of Finite Differences Method in MATLAB for Computing Derivatives of Opposing Automotive Motions on Piezoelectric Cells	Mohammed Alaa Alwafaie, Bela Kovács	Hungary, Hungary	Submission 232

Session 1.13			10 JULY 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-121	15:00-15:10	A Performance Constrained Metaheuristic Algorithm for 2D Mesh Based NoC	Aneeqa Khurshid, Muhammad Iram Baig	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 238
Y-122	15:11-15:20	Structure–activity relationship study of copper (II) complexes with 2-oxo-1,2-dihydroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde hydrazone: synthesis, structures, DNA and protein interaction studies, antioxidative and cytotoxic activity	Ayoub El-mrabet, Youssef Kandri Rodi, Skalli Mohamed Khalid, Amal Haoudi, Ahmed Mazzah	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, France	Submission 252
Y-123	15:20-15:30	The impact of the buffer layer material and active layer thickness on the performance of a fullerene-free organic solar cell	BENAYA Nouredine, ZOUKEL Abdelhalim, TAOUTI Mohammed Madani and Silaa Mohammed Yousri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 263
Y-124	15:30-15:40	Effects of local trees on the environmental climate of urban outdoor spaces in arid and semi-arid regions	Kamal Youcef, Marouane Samir Guedouh	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 264
Y-125	15:40-15:50	Valorization of β -glucans in the preparation of desserts	Alina Boistean, Aurica Chirsanova, Ana Chioru	Moldova, Moldova, Moldova	Submission 284
Y-126	15:50-16:00	Nutritional status for different categories of the population of the Republic of Moldova	Alina Boistean, Aurica Chirsanova, Rodica Sturza	Moldova, Moldova, Moldova	Submission 285
Y-127	16:00-16:10	Distribution and sources of Ag, Au, Bi, Cu and Mo in surface soils. Case study: Mitrovica region, Republic of Kosovo	Milihate Aliu, Robert Šajin, Trajče Stafilov	Kosovo, Slovenia, North Macedonia	Submission 290
Y-128	16:10-16:20	The relationship between miRNA-210 and SCN1B in fetal rats with hypoxic-ischemic brain injury	Hisham Al-Ward, Ning Liu, Moussa Omorou, Yiwei Huang, Wei Chen, Chun-Yang Liu, Shaochun Lv, Abduh Murshed, Fahmi Shaher, Yao Li, Yuxuan Zhang, Linxia Lu, Wenxia Gao, Yi Eve Sun and Hui Xu	China, China	Submission 302
Y-129	16:20-16:30	A Transformer based approach for Abstractive Text Summarization of Radiology Reports	Bilal Ahmed Khan Balouch, Fawad Hussain	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 339
Y-130	16:30-16:40	Simulations of Solving a Single-Player Memory Card Game with Several Implementations of a Human-Like Thinking Computer Algorithm	Ladislav Végh and Ondrej Takáč	Slovakia, Slovakia	Submission 353

Session 1.14			10 JULY 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-131	15:00-15:10	Deep Eutectic Solvents: Green Applications	Enas Nashef	United Arab Emirates	Submission 371
Y-132	15:11-15:20	Design and Computational Analysis of an Axisymmetric Contoured Supersonic Propulsion Nozzle	L. Dai, N. Boughazi and A. Haddad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 378
Y-133	15:20-15:30	An analytical study of direct normal irradiance for concentrated solar energy applications for the mechria region of Algeria	Larbi Mouhamed, Rouibah Abdelkader, Mouloud GUEMANA, LAISSAOUI Mohammed	Algeria	Submission 379
Y-134	15:30-15:40	Implementation of Rainfall Forecasting using ANN	N. Z. A. Nordin, M. M. Yunus and A. N. Dahalan	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 417
Y-135	15:40-15:50	Levels and Sources of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Surface Soils of Different Land Use Areas	HALFADJI Ahmed, CHOUGUI Abdelkader, NAOUS Mohamed, TOUABET Abdelkrim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 170
Y-136	15:50-16:00	Enhancing the Antibacterial Activity and Physical Properties of Spin coated Zinc Oxide Thin Films through Optimized Post-Heat Treatment	MOKHTARI Majda and ZIOUCHE Aicha	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 172
Y-137	16:00-16:10	A new one-parameter unit probability distribution: properties, estimation and application	Lazhar Benkhelifa	Algeria	Submission 175
Y-138	16:10-16:20	Simulation of the Dispersion of a Gaseous Pollutant (Benzene) in an Urban Environment Performed by ANSYS (CFD)	Abdellah Ibrir, Redha Rebhi, Mohamed Roubehie Fissa and Yacine Kerchich	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 176
Y-139	16:20-16:30	Exploration of the phytotherapeutic potential of monovarietal olive oil cultivated in arid region: evaluation of its antioxidant effects	Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI, Ramzi TRIKI, Meryem OUAZOUAZ and Cherifa HENCHIRI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 178
Y-140	16:30-16:40	GIS-based assessment of the hydrochemical and bacteriological properties of the Ghis Nekor groundwater (Al Hoceima, Morocco)	Chaimae BENAISSA, Belkacem BOUHMADEI, Abdelhamid Rossi, Yahya EL HAMMOUDANI and Fouad DIMANE	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 182

Session 1.15			10 JULY 2023 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-141	16:00-16:10	Elaboration and characterization of physicochemical properties and mineralogical study of natural clay (M'sila area)	Karima Larkat, Azzedine Benyahia, Meftah Allal, Nadir Deghfel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 184
Y-142	16:11-16:20	The Wavelet Transform Analysis using Directional Wavelet	Kenza Zaibak, Noura Nait Bouda, Fawzia Mekideche- Chafa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 185
Y-143	16:20-16:30	Effect of Water Inputs on Selected Growth Parameters of Canola (Brassica napus L.) in a Semi-Arid Region	BOURAHLA Amel, ZIOUCHE Sihem, DECHE Fateh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 192
Y-144	16:30-16:40	Analysis of Sandwich Plates FG with Porosities Using of High Order Shear-deformation Theory	MERDACHI Slimane, HADJ MOSTEFA Adda, BOUCHAFA Ali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 194
Y-145	16:40-16:50	Study on the Improvement of Treated Water Quality in the STEP2 of the Oued Souf Region (Southeast Algeria) through Dune Sand Filtration	Hannanou Ahmed, Mimeche Leila and Ouakouak Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 201
Y-146	16:50-17:00	INVESTIGATION OF THE RESIDUAL STRESSES DISTRIBUTION INDUCED BY COLD EXPANSION TECHNIQUE	EiHadj Besseghier, Abdelghani Baltach, Abdelkader Djebli	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 202
Y-147	17:00-17:10	Phase Structural, Microstructure, and Dielectric Characteristics of PZT Creramics	Ksouri Ahlem, Meklid Abdelhek, Zelikha Necira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 206
Y-148	17:10-17:20	Impact of Cr, Ni, Sb Doping on PZT: Phase Structural and Dielectric Characterization	Ksouri Ahlem, Meklid Abdelhek, Zelikha Necira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 207
Y-149	17:20-17:30	Structural and Dielectrical characterization of PZT piezoelectric ceramics	Ksouri Ahlem, Meklid Abdelhek, Zelikha Necira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 207
Y-150	17:30-17:40	Adsorptive removal of methylene blue from aqueous solutions by avtivated bentonite: effect of pH and initial concentration	Abd Errahmane ZEMOURI and Embarek BENTOUHAMI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 215

Session 1.16			10 JULY 2023 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-151	16:00-16:10	Photodegradation of an antibiotic in the presence of a semiconductor: titanium dioxide (TiO ₂)	Abd Errahmane ZEMOURI and Embarek BENTOUHAMI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 214
Y-152	16:11-16:20	Magnetic field assisted adsorption of methyl blue onto activated magnetic bentonite: Kinetic Study	Abd Errahmane ZEMOURI and Embarek BENTOUHAMI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 215
Y-153	16:20-16:30	Encapsulation of Fluconazole in niosomes and liposomes	BELKHODJA Abdelmajid, GUENDOZ Souheyla, BENKHALED Amel, CHOUKCHOU-BRAHAM Esma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 218
Y-154	16:30-16:40	The Therapeutic Potential of Hawthorn: Evaluating the Effects on Zinc Tissue, Biochemical Parameters, and Oxidative Stress in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Rats with Zinc-Deficient Diet	Ramzi TRIKI, Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI and Zine KECHRID	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 219
Y-155	16:40-16:50	The Beneficial Effects of Hawthorn Extract in Diabetes and its Complications: Evaluating the Hepatoprotective Impact on Liver Parameters, Oxidative Stress, and Zinc Tissue Status	Ramzi TRIKI, Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI and Zine KECHRID	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 220
Y-156	16:50-17:00	Evaluating the Renoprotective Effects of Hawthorn Extract on Renal Parameters, Oxidative Stress, and Zinc Tissue Status in Wistar Diabetic Rats	Ramzi TRIKI, Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI and Zine KECHRID	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 221
Y-157	17:00-17:10	Improving optical and Electrical Properties of Copper Oxide for thermoelectrical device	Almi Kenza, Bougezala Nasrine, Lakel Said and Boumezrag Maria	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 235
Y-158	17:10-17:20	Elimination of pharmaceutical pollutants by coagulation-flocculation using aluminum sulfate	Barkahoum BOUDOUMI, Nail AMARA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 237
Y-159	17:20-17:30	Control of a Nonlinear System Based on Fuzzy Logic	Abdelghafour HERIZI	Algeria	Submission 246
Y-160	17:30-17:40	Advancing the Properties of CuInX-1GaXS ₂ Compounds using the CASTEP Program: A Computational Exploration of Structural, Electronic, and Optical Characteristics	Faiza Benlakhdar, Idris Bouchama, Tayeb Chihi, Ibrahim Ghebouli	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 259

Session 1.17			10 JULY 2023 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-161	17:00-17:10	Density functional theory-driven design and study of modified acridine sensitizers for dye-sensitized solar cells	Mohammed Madani TAOUTI, Ali CHEKNANE and Naceur SELMANE	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 262
Y-162	17:10-17:20	Characterization of Monovarietal Extra Virgin Olive Oil Cultivated in Arid Zone of Biskra: Evaluation of Physicochemical and Quality Parameters.	Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI, Ramzi TRIKI, Meryem OUAZOUAZ and Cherifa HENCHIRI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 269
Y-163	17:20-17:30	Effects of heat treatment on the adsorption of a organic pollutant by an Algerian clay	Hadjer BOUSEMAT, Samira ZIANE, Amine Khelifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 274
Y-164	17:30-17:40	ON THE STABILITY RADII FOR IMPLICIT DIFFERENCE EQUATIONS	Nor-El-Houda beghersa	Algeria	Submission 276
Y-165	17:40-17:50	In situ hemisynthesis of new 2-oxopyridines and anticancer (G4) DNA molecular docking	Ramzi Maadadi, Rafik Menacer, Zahia Kabouche and Khaldoun Bachari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 280
Y-166	17:50-18:00	Zn-g-CN photocatalyst for dye photodegradation in aqueous medium its fabrication and characterization	Aamir Iqbal, Zeeshan Ahmed Siddiqui, Muhammad Saeed, Muhammad Ammar and Fatima Siddiqui	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 308
Y-167	18:00-18:10	Study of the resin type effect on composite specimens cut from elaborated tubes using filament winding technique subjected to bending loading	Mohammed Bettayeb, Abderrezak Bezazi, Abdelhakim Maizia, Abdelkader Hocine, Paulo N B D Reis, Omar Bouledroua, Fabrizio Scarpa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Algeria, UK	Submission 314
Y-168	18:10-18:20	Development, elaboration and characterization of composite tubes intended for hydrogen transport	Mohammed Bettayeb, Abderrezak Bezazi, Paulo N B D Reis, Abdelkader Hocine, Ghania Habbar, Brahim Baali, Mustapha Allouti, Fabrizio Scarpa	Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, UK	Submission 315
Y-169	18:20-18:30	Effect of annealing treatment in the mechanical property of chromium carbides films	Meryem Malla, Linda Aissani, Ahmed Belbah, Abderrezak Bezazi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 361
Y-170	18:30-18:40	Evaluation of the Unslotted CSMA_CA in Zigbee Networks	Sadika KHOUNI, Samia KHESRANI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 370

Session 1.18			10 JULY 2023 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-171	17:00-17:10	SPACE ANALYTICAL MODEL: IMPLANTATION OF THE SIMULACRAL TECHNIQUE IN DECISION MAKING	Elvis Elezaj	Kosovo	Submission 391
Y-172	17:10-17:20	Superhydrophobic Surface Modification for Enhanced Fabric Face Masks: The Impact of Varying HDTMS Concentrations	Suzylawati Ismail, Thanigesh Thiyagu and Syahida Farhan Azha	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 408
Y-173	17:20-17:30	Reliability Achievement of MIMO-OFDM Communication Systems	Shahir Fleyeh Nawaf, Lujain Sabah Abdula, Abdulmutalib A-Wahab Husein	Iraq, Iraq, Iraq	Submission 412
Y-174	17:30-17:40	DEVELOPMENT OF AN INTERNET OF THINGS BASED AIR QUALITY MONITORING SYSTEM USING MACHINE LEARNING	Abdulrasheed O. Abdulganiyu, Jonathan G. Kolo and Abraham U. Usman	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 418
Y-175	17:40-17:50	Classification of Mammography Images using Bag of Features Model	Sarah Benmazou	Algeria	Submission 426
Y-176	17:50-18:00	The Production of NO/NO2 Emissions In Propane-Syngas Mixture Diffusion Flame	Bouhentala B., Hadeef A., Aouachria Z. and Mameri A.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 478
Y-177	18:00-18:10	Fluid-elastic Instability Effect of Groove Cylinder in Heat Exchanger	Javaria Qadeer, Muhammad Moin Akhtar, Riffat Asim Pasha	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 493
Y-178	18:10-18:20	Contact force of composite plate impacted at low energy alteration by hygrothermal conditions	Mustapha RABOUH, Kamel ZOUGGAR and Khelifa GUERRAÏCHE	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 527
Y-179	18:20-18:30	Masonry Wall Reinforcement	M. Djeflal, A. Merdas	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 8
Y-180	18:30-18:40	Antioxidant properties of five Lactobacillus Plantarum strains as probiotics	Manel Sebouai	Algeria	Mail Submission 9

Session 1.19			10 JULY 2023 18:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-181	18:00-18:10	Reaction-Diffusion Models in Developmental Biological Sciences for Pattern Formation	Samiha Djemai and Salim Mesbahi	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 10
Y-182	18:10-18:20	Reaction-Diffusion Model Applied to Pattern Formation	Samiha Djemai and Salim Mesbahi	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 11
Y-183	18:20-18:30	Activated Carbon From Jujube Cores For Removal Of Cationic Dyes From Wastewater	Rafik El Arslene DRA, Amira Ghislaine DRA, Malika MEDJAHDI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 12
Y-184	18:30-18:40	Effect of adding palm components on the physical properties of clay bricks	Fidjah Abdelkader, Rabehi Mohamed, Kezarane Cheikh, Roqiya Dahmani, Slimani Zahia, Souddi Abdelhak, Medfouni Mohamed Nadjib, Alia Khadra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 13
Y-185	18:40-18:50	Characterization of Post-Impact Behavior of Luffa Mat Composite Using Acoustic Emission and Digital Image Correlation	Massinissa Grabi, Hocine Grabi, Ahmed Chellil, Samir Lecheb and Hamza mechakra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 14
Y-186	18:50-19:00	Corrosion Behavior of Electrodeposited Ni-Co and Ni-Co/TiO ₂ Alloys	Katia Nasri, Nadia Ait Ahmed, Hamida Issaadi, Nabila Aliouane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 15
Y-187	19:00-19:10	in vitro investigation of the antioxidant activity of aqueous and methanolic extracts of Punica granatum.L	Benhadda Amina Zhara, Bouzitouna Amina, Kadi Assia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 16
Y-188	19:10-19:20	Dependence of Fe Doping and Milling on TiO ₂ Nanomaterials Phase Transformation: Optical and Magnetic Studies	Y. KSSOUM, M. BOUDINA	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 17
Y-189	19:20-19:30	Elastic proprieties of van der Waal heterostuctures	LOUAFI Widad, REZOUALI Karim, LOUNIS Samir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 18
Y-190	19:30-19:40	Modified carbon paste electrode "GC/CuO" as voltammetric sensor for nitrite	HAMOUMA Ouezna, AMRA Siham, MAIZIA Radouane, TAGUELMIMT Lydia, OUKIL Dehbia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 19

Session 1.20			10 JULY 2023 18:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-191	18:00-18:10	Approximation solutions of time dependent Schrodinger equation for Mobius square potential using the Nikiforov-Uvarov-Functional Analysis method	Salim Medjber and Salah Menouar	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 20
Y-192	18:10-18:20	Physicochemical Analysis of Monovarietal Extra Virgin Olive Oil from the Semi-Arid Region: Evaluating Quality Parameters and Oxidative State.	Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI, Ramzi TRIKI, Meryem OUAZOUAZ and Cherifa HENCHIRI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 297
Y-193	18:20-18:30	Study of the antibacterial and antioxidant activities of some aromatic plants from the Aures region, Algeria: Lavandula officinalis, Salvia rosmarinus, Eucalyptus globulus	Khemili Aicha, Bensizerara Djamel, Khelifi Amira, Slimani Fatma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 298
Y-194	18:30-18:40	Natural convection heat transfer and fluid flow in a differentially heated square cavity filled with porous medium under non-Boussinesq conditions	Manel FENNI, Saber HAMIMID, Messaoud GUELLAL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 303
Y-195	18:40-18:50	Under non-Boussinesq conditions, natural convection and surface radiation heat transfer investigation occur in a square cavity with a porous media	Manel FENNI, Saber HAMIMID, Messaoud GUELLAL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 305
Y-196	18:50-19:00	Mechanical behaviour and durability of compressed earth blocks treated with bio-binder	Nouaouria Abdessalam, Mohamed Salah Nouaouria, Djilil Hamdaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 313
Y-197	19:00-19:10	ZnO prepared using Biomass extract for Direct blue 86 and Basic Blue 46 photodegradation under UVC irradiation	DOUFENE N., DAHDOUH N., BOUDECHICHE N., MOKHTARI M. and BERRAMA T.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 317
Y-198	19:10-19:20	First Principles Study of the Structural, Elastic and Electronic Properties of Half Heusler Compound NaZrB	D. Heciri, H. Belkhir and O. Benamara	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 318
Y-199	19:20-19:30	Microbiological, biochemical control of potato tuber	Charef Maysoune, Ouanas souheila and Branes Zidan	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 319
Y-200	19:30-19:40	Quantitative Data on Microorganisms and Heavy Metals in Middle Albania Soil	Anila Jançe, Admir Jançe, Valentin Bogoev	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 583

Session 1.21			10 JULY 2023 19:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-201	19:00-19:10	Design of an integrated SEPIC and Buck Converter for High Step-down Applications	Muhammad Ghayyoor, Mian Muhammad Amir Ayaz, Ajmal Farooq, M. Ali	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 322
Y-202	19:10-19:20	Enhanced photocatalytic activity of vanadium-doped titanate nanotubes heterostructure for organic pollutant degradation	BOUAYED Aouicha Mounia, AMEUR Nawal, BEDRANE Sumeya, BACHIR Redouane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 327
Y-203	19:20-19:30	On enhancing corrosion sensibility of stainless steel by a thermochemical treatment	Khokha LALAOUI, Karima BOUDJEDA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 336
Y-204	19:30-19:40	Kernel Conditional Residual Entropy in The α -Mixing Functional Data.	Elhadj HAMEL	Algeria	Submission 340
Y-205	19:40-19:50	Simulation and Modeling Approach for Enhanced Product Quality and Energy Efficiency in a moroccan dairy industry	Najwa Jbira, Anass Lebnaïti and Sanaa Hayani Mounir	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 357
Y-206	19:50-20:00	On pantograph problems involving generalized Hilfer operators in Banach algebra	Abdelatif Boutiara	Algeria	Submission 365
Y-207	20:00-20:10	Design Approach of dual bell nozzles with high area ratio	I. Laouar, A. Haddad	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 368
Y-208	20:10-20:20	Kinetic and thermodynamic study of malachite green adsorption on activated carbon doped with nanoparticles	ALLAL Mohamed, BENZEKRI BENALLOU Mokhtar, MEKIBES Zohra, DOUARA Nadia, TERMOUL Mourad, ATTOUTI Salima, BENDERDOUCHE Nourdine, BESTANI Benaouda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 369
Y-209	20:20-20:30	Rheology of eco-friendly mortars - Effect of industrial wastes additions	Hamza SOUALHI, Salim SAFFIDINE, Omar TALEB, Akram Salah Eddine BELAIDI, Benchaa BENABED	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 372
Y-210	20:30-20:40	Synthesis and characterization of a mixed oxide ZnSb ₂ O ₆	CHARIF Rania, TAOUAI Saliha, and MAKHLOUFI Rachid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 373

Session 1.22			10 JULY 2023 19:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-211	19:00-19:10	Numerical Approach of MHD conjugate Heat Transfer between Two Vertical Parallel Plates	Saidoune F.Z and Bouaziz M.N	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 377
Y-212	19:10-19:20	Exploring the Influence of MHD, conduction and Radiation Effects in Mixed Convection of Newtonian Flow along a Vertical Cylinder	Saidoune.FatmaZohra, Benharkat Zahra and Bouaziz.MN	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 382
Y-213	19:20-19:30	Design and Analysis of a Forced Convection Indirect Solar Dryer for Agricultural Food Products	Saidoune FatmaZohra, Galem Naima and Hamza Imane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 384
Y-214	19:30-19:40	Moroccan Cannabis Sativa Essential Oil Attenuates Peripheral Neuropathic Pain Induced By Chronic Sciatic Nerve Constriction Injury In Mice	Hamid Kabdya, Baslam Abdelmounaima, Abdelfatah Ait Baba, Abderrahman Chaita	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 387
Y-215	19:40-19:50	Reliability Study of a Biometric System Based on the Authentication of Handwritten Signatures	Boucerredj Leila	Algeria	Submission 388
Y-216	19:50-20:00	Quantification of Common and Differential Mode Measurements for Variable Speed Drive DC Motor	Mohcine AMARA, Houcine MILOUDI, Mohamed MILOUDI, Abdelber BENDAOUD and Mohammed Hamza BERMAKI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 393
Y-217	20:00-20:10	The second life of shrimp shells: a promising alternative	M. MOULAY-ABDALLAH, L. ADOUR, M. KHERAT	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 395
Y-218	20:10-20:20	Deep Learning Based Prediction of axial turbine performance for Clean Organic Rankine Cycle system driven by low-temperature heat source	T.T.Naas, A. Mahammedi and K. Rahmani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 400
Y-219	20:20-20:30	Heat and mass transfer efficiency in the T-Shaped geometry: Entropy generation analysis	T.T.Naas, A. Mahammedi and K. Rahmani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 401
Y-220	20:30-20:40	Efficacy of Drugs in the First, Second and Third-Line Therapy in Patients with Advanced Hepatocellular Carcinoma	Yusra Zarlashat, Bushra Munir, Muhammad Yameen, Wasim Abass and Abdul Ghaffar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 403

Session 1.23			11 JULY 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-221	09:00-09:10	Phytochemical composition and antioxidant activity of an Algerian species of Iridaceae family	Medjadji Bochra, Houam Abderrahim	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 407
Y-222	09:10-09:20	THE IMPACT OF MINING ACTIVITIES ON THE OXIDATIVE STRESS RESPONSE IN ACHILLEA MILLEFOLIUM, HYPERICUM PERFORATUM, AND PLANTAGO LANCEOLATA WITHIN THE INDUSTRIALIZED DISTRICT OF DRENAS, KOSOVO	Teuta Bajra Brahimaj, Enis Dalo, Shyrete Muriqi2, Hazbije Sahiti	Kosovo, Kosovo, Kosovo, Kosovo	Submission 409
Y-223	09:20-09:30	New Materials for Solid Oxide Fuel Cells with Dual ion-conducting Electrolyte	Sarah Guenou, Ali Cheknane, Selman Naceur and Inas Bouzateur	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 411
Y-224	09:30-09:40	Light naphtha (C5/C6) catalytic isomerization kinetics in presence of a bi-functional catalyst	Boudjema Amir Lehtihet, Tayeb Fakhreddine Boukezoula, Lahcène Bencheikh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 414
Y-225	09:40-09:50	Qualitative Study of New Class of Cubic Differentials Systems	N. Boulelli, A. Bendjeddou and R. Cheurfa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 420
Y-226	09:50-10:00	Contribution to the automation of clamping and positioning systems in machining fixtures using Artificial Intelligence Techniques	Arslane Mustapha, Brik Youcef and Slamani Mohamed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 421
Y-227	10:00-10:10	Application of experimental design for the modelling of extraction of gentian violet dye in aqueous solution by polystyrene membrane modified with oleic acid	Yanis Zakaria Lakehal, Salima Ziani, Salima Aitali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 430
Y-228	10:10-10:20	A Delayed SIRS Epidemic Model for Optimal Control with Vaccination and Treatment	Nadjla ABIDAT, Nedjma Boulelli	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 431
Y-229	10:20-10:30	The Effect of SiO ₂ -CuO/H ₂ O Hybrid Nano-Fluid in A Square cavity	Bouselsal Maissa, Mebarek-Oudina Fateh	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 432
Y-230	10:30-10:40	Everything you need to know about Ginger, Turmeric and Cloves	Aya Aggoun and Chahra Boudoukhar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 434

Session 1.24			11 JULY 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-231	09:00-09:10	The Durability of high performance concrete based on silica fume containing marble powder as finite aggregate	Yassine Abbas, Rachid Djebien and Sidali Denine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 444
Y-232	09:10-09:20	Designing Assistive Devices to Support Learning for Students with Hearing Impairments	Izwah Ismail, Sharifah Nurulhuda Tuan Mohd Yasin, Ilya Ismail and Rhoma Erma Zaini	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 445
Y-233	09:20-09:30	Exploring the Therapeutic Potential of Semi-Arid Virgin Olive Oil: A Comprehensive Analysis of Bioactive Compounds and Health Benefits.	Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI, Ramzi TRIKI, Meryem OUAZOUAZ and Cherifa HENCHIRI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 446
Y-234	09:30-09:40	Exploring the Therapeutic Potential and Hepatic Profile Analysis of Virgin Olive Oil from the Semi-Arid Region in NPTiO ₂ -Induced Oxidative Stress in Rats	Khaoula BOUGHEDIRI, Ramzi TRIKI, Meryem OUAZOUAZ and Cherifa HENCHIRI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 448
Y-235	09:40-09:50	Control of Grid-Connected PV Based inverter on Single Phase Modular Multilevel Converter	Imane ALIA, Imad MERZOUK, Osama ABUSHAFA	Algeria, Algeria, UK	Submission 449
Y-236	09:50-10:00	First Principles Study of the Structural, Magnetic and Magneto-optical Properties of The Compound PdCo	O. Benamara, D. Heciri	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 450
Y-237	10:00-10:10	The importance of subjects in private international law	Argona Kuçi, Kastriote Vlahna	Kosovo, Kosovo	Submission 456
Y-238	10:10-10:20	The importance and development of the banking system in Kosovo	Dafina Vlahna	Kosovo	Submission 457
Y-239	10:20-10:30	Electronic Business, the most popular form of businesses	Besnik Hajdari	Kosovo	Submission 458
Y-240	10:30-10:40	Predicting the Remaining Useful Life of a DC Motor using ANFIS Neuro-Fuzzy Hybrid Model	A. SEDDAR YAGOUB, S. BENAMMAR	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 459

Session 1.25			11 JULY 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-241	10:00-10:10	Security and risks of using E-business	Besnik Hajdari	Kosovo	Submission 460
Y-242	10:10-10:20	Synthesis and characterization of graphitic carbon nitride	Mahdi ACHOUR, Fatima AMMARI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 462
Y-243	10:20-10:30	Electrosynthesis, characterization and valorization of colloidal silver	F.Lasmi, H.Laribi, H.Hamitouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 465
Y-244	10:30-10:40	Securing the defendant in criminal proceedings through detention	Kosovare Sopi	Kosovo	Submission 473
Y-245	10:40-10:50	Preliminary assesment of the in vivo analgesic potential (the acetic acid induced writhing test) of an Algerian wild Thymus species	Abderrahim Houam, Assia Zeghib, Fouad Zeghib and Zahia Kabouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 474
Y-246	10:50-11:00	Preliminary evaluation of the acute toxicity, in a biological model (mice), of an Algerian wild Thymus species	Abderrahim Houam, Assia Zeghib, Fouad Zeghib, Karima Belguendouz and Zahia Kabouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 484
Y-247	11:00-11:10	Preliminary assesment of the in vivo anti-inflammatory potential (the xylene induced ear edema assay) of an Algerian wild Thymus species	Assia Zeghib, Abderrahim Houam, Fouad Zeghib and Zahia Kabouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 486
Y-248	11:10-11:20	Preliminary investigation of medicinal plants used in Algerian traditional medicine to treat skin diseases at Tebessa municipality	Assia Zeghib, Abderrahim Houam, Soraya Hioun, Fouad Zeghib and Zahia Kabouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 487
Y-249	11:20-11:30	Deep Real Time multi-Face Recognition	Zead Mohammed Yosif, Muhamad Azhar Abdilatef	Iraq, Iraq	Submission 491
Y-250	11:30-11:40	An Elastic Analysis: Structural Analysis and Design for Curved Beam Portal Frames	B. Mebarki, B.K. Benazzouz	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 492

Session 1.26			11 JULY 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-251	10:00-10:10	Asymptotic analysis of solutions to the problem $\varepsilon^2 \Delta u + \lambda u = F(u)$ on a ring in	Ketfi Roufaïda, Bendaas Saida and Djabi Abdelmoumene	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 488
Y-252	10:10-10:20	ELIMINATION OF METHYLENE BLUE BY ELECCTROCOAGULATION USING RECYCLED ALUMINUM PLATES AS ELECTRODES	Abir Hasnaoui, Mustapha Chikhi, Fouzia Balaska, Walid Seraghni and Mohamed Boussemghoune	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 508
Y-253	10:20-10:30	Effect of addition saffron extract (<i>Crocus sativus</i>) on the cooking properties of barley noodles	Fatima TENSAOUT, Karima TAZRART and DJamel Edine KATI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 509
Y-254	10:30-10:40	Modelling the influence of waste rubber and brick waste on Compressive and flexural Strengths of mortar by Artificial Neural Network	Boukour Salima, Lafifi Brahim, Benmalek Mohamed Larbi, Aidoud Aidoud, Bencheikh Messaouda and Benzaid Mehdi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 510
Y-255	10:40-10:50	Chitosan Effect on Morphology of Tomato under Drought Stress	Shadab Faramarzi, Leila Akbari, Masoomeh Amerian, Noshin Mahmodi, Kianoosh Cheqamirza, Sara Vitalini, Marcello Iriti	Iran, Iran, Iran, Iran, Italy, Italy	Submission 512
Y-256	10:50-11:00	Effect of the Incorporation of Plastic Waste on the Physico-Mechanical Properties of a Mortar at a Young Age	Aidoud Assia, Boutahir Messaouda Born Bencheikh, Boukour Salima, Khaldi Nacira, Zerig Tahar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 513
Y-257	11:00-11:10	Identifying Novel Drug Candidates for Influenza Virus via Computational Approaches	Bourougaa Lotfi, Oussaf Mebarka	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 516
Y-258	11:10-11:20	Sanguisorba minor L.'s in silico anti HIV-1 activity and ADME/Tox evaluation	Sameh BOUDIBA, Chahrazed HAOUAM, Alfred NGENGUE, Karima HANINI and Louiza BOUDIBA	Algeria, Algeria, Camerun, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 517
Y-259	11:20-11:30	Valorization of the ethyl acetate extract of <i>Atriplex Halimus L.</i> from Tébessa region as corrosion inhibitor: Electrochemical study	Louiza Boudiba, Baya Berka, Sameh Boudiba, Karima Hanini, Azza Baccouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 522
Y-260	11:30-11:40	Predicting Interfacial Failure in Laminate Composite by using the Finite Element Method (FEM) : A Cohesive Zone Modeling Approach for Delamination	Mustapha RABOUH, Abdelfattah Elhadj BENKHECHIBA, Kamel ZOUGGAR, Khelifa GUERRAÏCHE,	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 523

			Dahmane HACHI, Brahim Elkhailil HACHI		
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Session 1.27			11 JULY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-261	10:00-10:10	Study of CdZnTe based II-VI semiconductor lasers for dermatological application, and simulation of the biological tissue response	Riane Houaria, Bahlouli Samia, Kelouch Nawal and Hamdache Fatima	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 556
Y-262	10:10-10:20	Evaluation of groundwater vulnerability to anthropogenic impacts in a densely urbanized context: Integrating chemical and isotopic tools	Ben Nasr Wassef	Tunisia	Submission 557
Y-263	10:20-10:30	THE ELECTROCHEMICAL BEHAVIOUR OF MILD STEEL IN ACIDIC MEDIUM	Gharbi Amira, Dridi Manel, Hamlaoui Youcef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 558
Y-264	10:30-10:40	Generation of non-functional architectonic spatial forms with geometric transformations	Ferenc Sebesteny	Hungary	Submission 566
Y-265	10:40-10:50	In Silico assessment of insecticidal activity of Santolina Africana	SAYAD Imane, AOUAIDJIA Hanane and LEBBAL Salim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 569
Y-266	10:50-11:00	Optimization of operating parameters influencing copper sulphate crystallization: Box-Behnken design	Amira Boufrioua, Sarrah Guilane and Leila Benmansour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 572
Y-267	11:00-11:10	Solar Lead-Acid Battery Bank Management Strategy	Bilel Ayachi, Ahmed Bahri and Nabil Mezhoud	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 573
Y-268	11:10-11:20	The effect of finely ground dune sand on the properties of self-compacting concrete	Rachid RABEHI, Mohamed AMIEUR and Mohamed RABEHI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 574
Y-269	11:20-11:30	Synthesis and Characterization of Semiconductor Nanoparticles for Photocatalytic Pharmaceutical Wastewater Treatment	Bouaziz Aya, Gherbi Naima	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 577
Y-270	11:30-11:40	Sugar Waste Valorization In Making Fired Clay Brick	SI AHMED Chabane, Ghani Djafri	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 581

Session 1.28			11 JULY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-271	10:00-10:10	Effect of initial concentration on sulfamethoxazole (SMX) removal using zinc oxide adsorbent coating	Noorlaila Mohamed Nor, Muhamad Sharafee Shamsudin, Suzylawati Ismail	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 590
Y-272	10:10-10:20	Synthesis of Metal-Organic Framework MOF-2 (Zn-BDC)	Meriem Guira, Samia Kerakra, Abderrahmane Habi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 594
Y-273	10:20-10:30	Obesity as a 21st century pandemic	Iveta Štempeľová, Ondrej Takáč and Helena Hudáková	Czech Republic, Slovakia, Slovakia	Submission 595
Y-274	10:30-10:40	FINAL YEAR'S STUDENT'S PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS SERVICE QUALITY PROVIDED BY POLYTECHNIC	Nor Linda Binti Mokhtar, Siti Zubaidah Binti Md Hamin and Ratna Hafiza Binti Redzuan	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 601
Y-275	10:40-10:50	Structural Features of Catalysts for Hydrogenation of Carbon Dioxide to C2+ hydrocarbons based on alumina with deposited ferrocene, its bi- and trinuclear derivatives	Aygun Rustamova, Etibar Ismailov	Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan	Submission 605
Y-276	10:50-11:00	The effectiveness of Cement Kiln Dust on clayey soil properties	Innal Wissem, Zemouli Samira and Hacene chaouche Abdelmadjid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 607
Y-277	11:00-11:10	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Environmental Impacts Towards Plastic Waste by Using Pyrolysis	Amirah Ayu Kartika, Low Siew Chuna, Suzylawati Ismail	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 520
Y-278	11:10-11:20	Finite Element Simulation and Stress Analysis of Gas Turbine Blade Due to Centrifugal Force	Mohammed Talal Mohammed, Ziad Shakeeb Al Sarraf and Sabah Mohammed Jamil	Iraq, Iraq, Iraq	Submission 383
Y-279	11:20-11:30	Development of A Fuzzy Logic-Based Cost Modeling System for Sugar Industry	Ameer Hamza Khan, Muhammad Sajid, Rohail Ahmed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 576
Y-280	11:30-11:40	Holocene Data on Fossil Pollen of Dipsacaceae Plants, Central Albania	Admir Jançe, Anila Jançe, Gëzim Kapidani	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 582

Session 1.29			11 JULY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-281	12:00-12:10	Review on Novel AI-Based Soft Computing Applications in Motor Drives	Sabo Aliyu, Maigari Yunana Jeremiah, Kamaluddeen Ibrahim Kanya, Naziru Shuaibu, Aliyu Ahmed, Ahmadu Kenneth, Bukar Alhaji Bukar, Kwasau Samaila, Muhammad Mamman, Chigozie Onyema, James Sanda Yakubu,	Malaysia, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 33
Y-282	12:11-12:20	Analytical failure analysis of bio/synthetic sandwich pipe under pressure	HABBAR Ghania, HOCINE Abdelkader, MAIZIA Abdelhakim, BEZAZI Abderrezak, BETTAYEB Mohammed, BOULEDROUA Omar, RIBEIRO João, DHAOU Mohamed Houcine, Ghouaoula Abd Elhamid, and LOUZA Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, Saudi Arabia, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 22
Y-283	12:20-12:30	Digital challenges of production processes in a company	László Szabó, Norbert Forman and Mihály Szilárd Avornicului	Hungary, Hungary, Hungary	Submission 539
Y-284	12:30-12:40	Challenges in Teaching Informatics	Norbert Forman and Mihály Szilárd Avornicului	Hungary, Hungary	Submission 540
Y-285	12:40-12:50	A multi-objective strategy for cost-effective microgrid solutions based on renewable energy sources	Ihtisham Ullah Khan, Gul Rukh and Mian Farhan Ullah	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 599
Y-286	12:50-13:00	THE IMPACT OF URBAN AND INDUSTRIAL ACTIVITY IN THE POLLUTION OF SHKUMBINI RIVER	Lirim Bekteshi, Belinda Hoxha, Nikolin Gega, Piro Karamelo	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 608
Y-287	13:00-13:10	Design of Hybrid multi-level inverter for photovoltaic (PV) application	Ihteshamul haq, Ajmal Farooq, Mian Muhammad Amir Ayaz, Muhammad Ali	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 291
Y-288	13:10-13:20				
Y-289	13:20-13:30				
Y-280	13:30-13:40				

Session 2.1			12 JULY 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-17	09:00-09:10	Antalya'da Doğal Yayılış Gösteren Hoş Kokuya Sahip Bitkiler	İlhami Emrah Dönmez	Turkey	Mail Submission 1
T-18	09:10-09:20	Deniz Taşımacılığı ve Hizmet Türleri	Ömer CANBAZ, Murat YORULMAZ	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 3
T-19	09:20-09:30	Some Remarks on Rough IK-Statistical Convergence of Sequences in Normed Linear Spaces	Ömer Kişi and Mustafa Yıldız	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 4
T-20	09:30-09:40	Protease production by Bacillus pumilus K7 isolated from soil	Elanur DAŞDEMİR, Meryem DOYMUŞ, Hakan ÖZKAN and Mesut TAŞKIN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 5
T-21	09:40-09:50	AISI 1045 Çeliğinin Sürdürülebilir Tornalama İşleminde Sıcaklık Analizi	Mustafa Kuntoğlu, Kübra Kaya, Rüstem Binali	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1
T-22	09:50-10:00	Küresel Salgınlarda Blok Zinciri Tabanlı Akıllı Kontratların Kullanımı	Emre BAYRAM, Ahmet Haşim YURTTAKAL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 51
T-23	10:00-10:10	Kel Kartal Arama Optimizasyon Algoritması Kullanarak Çok Seviyeli SHE-PWM İnverter İçin Optimum Anahtarlama Açılımları Oluşturma	Yasin BEKTAŞ	Turkey	Submission 56
T-24	10:10-10:20	Beyin Dalgaları Kontrollü Maket Tekerlekli Sandalye	Bayram Fışkın, Mehmet Göllü, İsmail Zengin, Emirhan Yüksel, İsmail Varol, Mehmet Barış Tabakcıoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 62
T-25	10:20-10:30	Konveyör Bant Üzerindeki Atıkların Görüntü İşleme Metodu Kullanılarak Sınıflandırılması ve Ayrıştırılması	Şakir Dağdelen, Ahmet Bilgehan Serçe, Furkan Kaya, Berk Güngör, Mehmet Barış Tabakcıoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 66
T-26	10:30-10:40	Classification of Plant Diseases with Machine Learning	Elif Akarsu, Tevhit Karacali, İ. Yücel Özbek	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 75

Session 2.2			12 JULY 2023 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-27	09:00-09:10	Determination of Some Pomological and Chemical Characteristics of Wild Plums Grown in Kayseri Ecology	Ayşen Melda ÇOLAK, Fatma ALAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 77
T-28	09:10-09:20	Effect of Parameter Selection on Heart Attack Risk Prediction in an RNN Model	Pınar Cihan	Turkey	Submission 79
T-29	09:20-09:30	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Control Interface Design and Implementation with TI F28335 DSP on Simulink External Mode	Erdem Ilten	Turkey	Submission 92
T-30	09:30-09:40	Estimation of proton-boron reaction cross-sections by neural networks	Serkan Akkoyun	Turkey	Submission 97
T-31	09:40-09:50	A Novel Expectation-Maximization Algorithm for Probabilistic Pushdown Automata by using Symbolic Control	Mete Özbaltan	Turkey	Submission 105
T-32	09:50-10:00	Karma Yemlerde Kullanılan Bazı Yem Hammaddelerinin Mikroskopisi	Perihan Yılmaz, Asuman Arslan Duru	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 106
T-33	10:00-10:10	Examining the Effects of Biochar in Spinach Cultivation with Increased Irrigation Water Salinity on Some Physical and Physiological Properties of the Plant	Caner Yerli	Turkey	Submission 110
T-34	10:10-10:20	Effect of Plasma Nitriding Parameters on Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of DIN 1.2367 Hot Work Tool Steel	Ali ARI	Turkey	Submission 113
T-35	10:20-10:30	Effect of Gas Nitriding Parameters on Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of DIN 1.2367 Hot Work Tool Steel	Ali ARI	Turkey	Submission 115
T-36	10:30-10:40	Investigation of the Effects of 0W20 and 10W40 Lubricating Oils on Cylinder Liner Wear	Idris Cesur and Beytullah Eren	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 118

Session 2.3			12 JULY 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-37	10:00-10:10	İÇ MİMARLIK OFİSLERİNDE VERİMLİLİĞİ ETKİLEYEN FAKTÖRLER	Mehmet Çolak, Nilay Görmüş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 120
T-38	10:10-10:20	Investigation of the effect of supporting electrolyte type and pH parameters on electrooxidation color removal from Direct Blue 86	Sermin GÜNASLAN, Baybars Ali FİL and Deniz TOSUN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 127
T-39	10:20-10:30	Turkey's Access to International E-Commerce Markets and The Future Of E-Export	Mehmet Salih ÖKSÜZ, Abdullah ÖNDEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 136
T-40	10:30-10:40	An Examination of Studies on the Use of Chatbot Technology in the Field of Education	Hatice YILDIZ DURAK, Aytuğ ONAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 147
T-41	10:40-10:50	Programlama eğitiminde öğrenci performansının makine öğrenmesi algoritmaları ile tahminlenmesi	Ayut DURAK, Vahide BULUT	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 146
T-42	10:50-11:00	Turkish Adaptation of the Chatbot System, Information and Service Quality Scale	Hatice YILDIZ DURAK, Aytuğ ONAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 147
T-43	11:00-11:10	SMART HOSPITAL SYSTEM AKILLI HASTANE SİSTEMİ	Rabia Kuran, Şaban Gülcü	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 150
T-44	11:10-11:20	Conoid Surfaces Family in Three-Dimensional Euclidean Space	Erhan Güler and Ömer Kişi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 157
T-45	11:20-11:30	Conoid Surfaces Family in Minkowski 3-Space	Erhan Güler and Ömer Kişi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 158
T-46	11:30-11:40	Some Observations on g-Metric Spaces in Light of Generalized Statistical Convergence of Double Sequences via Ideals	Ömer Kişi and Erhan Güler	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 159

Session 2.4			12 JULY 2023 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-47	10:00-10:10	Further Results on Lacunary Difference Sequences of Complex Uncertain Variables in 2-Normed Spaces	Ömer Kişi and Erhan Güler	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 160
T-48	10:10-10:20	Beslenme ve Diyetetik Alanında Gıdalarda ve Beslenmede Ölçü Birimleri, Ölçü Araçları ve Ölçü Almada Kullanılan Yöntemler	Şenay Burçin Alkan, Hasan Hüseyin Kara	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 161
T-49	10:20-10:30	Gıda Ambalajlamada Yenilikçi Teknolojiler, Önemi ve Bazı Uygulamaları	Havvanur Taşkın, Hasan Hüseyin Kara	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 173
T-50	10:30-10:40	Federe Öğrenme Algoritmaları ve Açık Kaynak Çerçevesler	Ömer Faruk Göçgün, Femin Yalcin, Aytuğ Onan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 177
T-51	10:40-10:50	Automatic Knee Osteoarthritis Severity Grading using Deep Neural Networks: Comparative Analysis of Network Architectures and Optimization Functions	Ahmet Ezgi, Aytuğ Onan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 180
T-52	10:50-11:00	Türkçe Twitter Verileri Üzerinde Duygu Analizi: LSTM, CNN-LSTM, BERT Algoritmalarının Karşılaştırılması	Hazal Gizem DÖNMEZ, Yaşar BECERİKLİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 196
T-53	11:00-11:10	Optik Görüntülerdeki Deniz Vasıtalarının Derin Öğrenme Yöntemleriyle Tespiti ve Sınıflandırılması	Yahya İZALA, Yaşar BECERİKLİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 198
T-54	11:10-11:20	Influence of Stand-off Distance on the Blast-Resistance of Steel Plate Supported Concrete Walls	Rasid Ahmed Yildiz	Turkey	Submission 199
T-55	11:20-11:30	FLUORIDE and LIVER TOXICITY: A ZEBRAFISH MODEL	Laman MAMMADZADA, Emine TORAMAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 203
T-56	11:30-11:40	Investigation of the Effect of Different Engine Oils on the Amount of Cylinder Liner Wear	Idris Cesur	Turkey	Submission 205

Session 2.5			12 JULY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-57	11:00-11:10	Düktül Boru Üretimi İçin Hidrolik Devre Tasarımı ve Simülasyonu	Mahmut Can ŞENEL	Turkey	Submission 208
T-58	11:11-11:20	Uçak İniş Takımları İçin Hidrolik Devre Tasarımı ve Simülasyonu	Mahmut Can ŞENEL	Turkey	Submission 211
T-59	11:20-11:30	Experimental Investigation of Diesel Engine Characteristics under Various Loads	İsmet Sezer	Turkey	Submission 212
T-60	11:30-11:40	Betonarme Binaların Deprem Performansının Belirlenmesi: Binanız Depreme Ne Kadar Dayanıkl?	Ahmet Ferdi Şenol	Turkey	Submission 224
T-61	11:40-11:50	The Importance of Rose and Rosehip Species in Past, Present, and Tomorrow	İbrahim Halil HATIPOĞLU	Turkey	Submission 225
T-62	11:50-12:00	Process Management and One Example Service Sector	Pınar ŞENDİKİCİ	Turkey	Submission 227
T-63	12:00-12:10	Use of Cactus and Succulents in Vertical Gardens	Mert ÇAKIR	Turkey	Submission 228
T-64	12:10-12:20	Parkinson Hastalığının Tespitinde Konuşma Ses Karakteristiklerinin İncelenmesine Dair Bir Çalışma	Zekeriya Anil Guven	Turkey	Submission 231
T-65	12:20-12:30	Defense against white box adversarial attacks in Arabic Natural Language Processing (ANLP)	MOKHTAR ALSHEKH, KÖKSAL ERENTÜRK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 234

Session 2.6			12 JULY 2023 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-67	11:00-11:10	Virtual screening of natural meroterpenoids towards SARS-CoV-2 main protease	Idris Arslan	Turkey	Submission 240
T-68	11:11-11:20	Molecular docking analysis of natural unusual triterpenoids towards PAK1 protein	Idris Arslan	Turkey	Submission 241
T-69	11:20-11:30	The Relationship Between Exercise Addiction Levels and Healthy Nutrition Levels of Students Studying at the Faculty of Health Sciences	Abdurrahim YILDIZI	Turkey	Submission 242
T-70	11:30-11:40	Kalman Filtresi Parametre Değişimlerinin Batarya SoC Tahmini Üzerine Etkileri	Mehmet KORKMAZ	Turkey	Submission 248
T-71	11:40-11:50	Quasi-Z-Source (QZS) – Based Multilevel Inverter Design	Hidayet Talha Uluşan, Sadık Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 249
T-72	11:50-12:00	Design of Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) Algorithm for Solar-Based Grid-Connected Quasi-Z-Source Single-Phase Inverter	Mehmet Ali Yazıcı, Sadık Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 250
T-73	12:00-12:10	Detection and Classification of Unwanted Weeds in Maize Field by Image Processing	Mehmet Bağcı, Sadık Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 251
T-74	12:10-12:20	Calculation of Second Virial Coefficient of DNA	Bahtiyar Akber Mamedov, Elif Somuncu, Ebru Karatas	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 253
T-75	12:20-12:30	Calculation of the Second Virial Coefficient of The TMGa Molecule	Bahtiyar Akber Mamedov, Elif Somuncu, Ebru Karatas	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 254
T-76	12:30-12:40	Empirical Investigations: Power Quality Disturbance Classification	Sıtkı AKKAYA	Turkey	Submission 255

Session 2.7			12 JULY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-150	12:00-12:10	A Conspectus of PQD Analysis	Sıtkı AKKAYA	Turkey	Submission 256
T-151	12:11-12:20	Modal Analysis of the Wind Turbine Planned to be Built in Mamurdağı Ground Conditions Using Finite Element Method	Hakan Aydın	Turkey	Submission 260
T-152	12:20-12:30	Non-Integer Order Proportional Integral Control for Time Delay Plant with Single Fractional Order	Bilal Şenol, Uğur Demiroğlu, Radek Matusů and Emre Avuçlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Czech Republic	Submission 265
T-153	12:30-12:40	Konut İnşaatı Sektöründe İş Sağlığı ve Güvenliği Maliyetleri, İşveren ve Çalışan Teknik Personelin İş Sağlığı ve Güvenliği Kültürünün Değerlendirilmesi	Sinan VURAL, Mehmet PİŞKİN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 266
T-154	12:40-12:50	Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Teknikleri ile Üniversite Seçimi: Makine Mühendisliği Eğitimi İçin Bir Model Önerisi	Adnan Abdulvahitoğlu, Aslı Abdulvahitoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 267
T-155	12:50-13:00	An Investigation of Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) System Application for Energy Efficiency of Smart Agriculture	Ozlem Boydak	Turkey	Submission 268
T-156	13:00-13:10	GPS Verisinin Alınmadığı Ortamlarda Otonom Görev Yapabilen Gemi İçin Sensör Kaynaştırma Algoritmaları Tasarımı, Gerçeklenmesi ve Testi	Caner ÇELİK, Yaşar BECERİKLİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 270
T-157	13:10-13:20	TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION OF A HANGER FOR THE CRANE OF A BOAT	Feridun KARAKOÇ, Rafael Villalobos TORRES, Ahmet DAYANÇ, Melih CANLIDİNÇ	Turkey, Spain, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 271
T-158	13:20-13:30	Improving the Prediction Performance of Protein Protein Interaction Sites Using Xgboost and Optimization	Yunus Emre GÖKTEPE	Turkey	Submission 273
T-159	13:30-13:40	İNŞAAT YÖNETİM SÜREÇLERİNDE MALZEME TEDARİĞİ VE STOKLANMASININ BİM (YAPI BİLGİ MODELLEME) İLE ENTEGRASYONU	Enes BAĞÇECİ, Şahin Tolga GÜVEL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 277

Session 2.8			12 JULY 2023 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-160	12:00-12:10	İkili fayans tozu, tuğla tozu ve cam tozu bazlı geopolimer kompozitlerin mekanik özelliklerinin incelenmesi	Gazi GÜNEL, Özer SEVİM, İlhami DEMİR, Erdiñç Halis ALAKARA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 279
T-161	12:11-12:20	Stiffened Hollow Structural Section Joints in Fire	Emre ÖZYURT	Turkey	Submission 281
T-162	12:20-12:30	Methylene blue concentration and pH-induced photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue without photocatalyst under visible light	Sultan Göktaş and Gülsen Şahin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 283
T-163	12:30-12:40	Piroteknik Malzemelerin Ömürlerinin Belirlenmesinde Kullanılan Yaşlandırma Mekanizmalarının İncelenmesi	Kaan Turgay ÖZKAN, Muharrem PUL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 289
T-164	12:40-12:50	Evaluation of Zirconium Based Metal-Organic Framework UiO-67 for Removal of Methylene Blue	Ferda Civan Çavuşođlu	Turkey	Submission 292
T-165	12:50-13:00	Twisted Surfaces Family in Euclidean 3-Space	Erhan Güler and Mustafa Yıldız	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 293
T-166	13:00-13:10	Physical mechanisms and predictive performance of thermal conductivity models for nanofluids	Nevzat Akkurt, Tim Shedd	Turkey, USA	Submission 295
T-167	13:10-13:20	Mitochondrial Dysfunction and Diabetes	Mehmet ÖZSAN, Canan CEYLAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 296
T-168	13:20-13:30	Classification of Poisonous and Edible Mushrooms with Optimized Classification Algorithms	Sedat Metlek, Halit Çetiner	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 300
T-169	13:30-13:40	Sođutma Debisinin Fotovoltaik Isıl Sistem Verimine Etkisi	Sinan Dölek, Gökhan Arslan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 304

Session 2.9			12 JULY 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-170	13:00-13:10	Determination of Cutting Tool Performance Characteristics in Machining Nickel Based Super Alloys	Abdullah ALTIN	Turkey	Submission 306
T-171	13:11-13:20	Türkiye’de göz ardı edilen bir maden: Anhidrit	Zekeriya Duran	Turkey	Submission 307
T-172	13:20-13:30	Detection of Welding Defects by Non-Destructive Testing Methods	Furkan SOYTURK, Alper GUNOZ and Memduh KARA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 309
T-173	13:30-13:40	Nanocomposite Materials Used in Heat and Sound Insulation	Veli COPUR, Alper GUNOZ and Memduh KARA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 310
T-174	13:40-13:50	The Recyclability of Composite Materials	Umut Ozgur OZALTAY, Alper GUNOZ and Memduh KARA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 311
T-175	13:50-14:00	Investigation of Free Vibrations of Stepped Nanobeam Embedded In Elastic Foundation	Mustafa Oguz Nalbant, Süleyman Murat Bağdatlı, Ayla Tekin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 325
T-176	14:00-14:10	Some Properties of the Conditional Dual Lucas Octonions	Sure KÖME	Turkey	Submission 326
T-177	14:10-14:20	Sıfır Değerlikli Nikel Nanoparçacıkların Sentezi, Karakterizasyonu ve Hayvansal İçyağlardan Biyodizel Üretiminde Katalizör Olarak Kullanılması	Meral TURABİK, Cihan GEÇGEL, Gülsüm AKINBİNGÖL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 328
T-178	14:20-14:30	Some Properties of Hessenberg Matrices with Conditional Elements	Cahit KÖME	Turkey	Submission 331
T-179	14:30-14:40	FARKLI KONTROL TABANLI ŞÖNT AKTİF FİLTRE UYGULAMALARI: ELEKTRİKLİ ARAÇ BATARYA ŞARJ SİSTEMİ ÖRNEĞİ	Yusuf ERTAŞ, Ömer Ali KARAMAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 333

Session 2.10			12 JULY 2023 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-180	13:00-13:10	Hematological, Biochemical and Blood Gas Findings in a Calf with Cerebral Theileriosis	Murat UZTİMÜR, Hakan KEÇECİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 335
T-181	13:11-13:20	Genomic Selection in Cattle Breeding: Recent Advances and Future Needs	Nursen ŞENTÜRK, Sena ARDIÇLI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 337
T-182	13:20-13:30	RANS-DES Comparison on the Numerical Modelling of a Downforce Generating Wing Moving over a Solid Surface	Yavuz Hakan Ozdemir, Taner Cosgun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 338
T-183	13:30-13:40	Development of an Enzyme-Linked ImmunoSorbent Assay for Detection of Gluten Content of Different Food Samples	Reha Onur Azizoglu	Turkey	Submission 341
T-184	13:40-13:50	Hydrothermal Alteration Detection from Thin Section Images using Convolutional Neural Networks	Rıza Çenet, Emre Ünsal, Oktay Canbaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 342
T-185	13:50-14:00	Demir Oksit ile Hüyük Asit Adsorpsiyonu	Suna Özden ÇELİK, Nesli AYDIN, Gül KAYKIOĞLU	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 343
T-186	14:00-14:10	Improving Mass Detection in Mammography Using Focal Loss Based RetinaNet	Semih DEMİREL, Ataberk URFALI, Ömer Faruk BOZKIR, Azer ÇELİKTEN, Abdulkadir BUDAK and Hakan KARATAŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 344
T-187	14:10-14:20	Pulmonary Nodule Detection on X-Ray Images using a One-Stage Object Detector Based on a Deep Convolutional Neural Network	Azer ÇELİKTEN, Semih DEMİREL, Ataberk URFALI, Ömer Faruk BOZKIR, Abdulkadir BUDAK, and Hakan KARATAŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 345
T-188	14:20-14:30	Single-Flow Supercritical CO2 Brayton Cycles: A Performance Comparison of the Different Layouts	Serpil ÇELİK TOKER, Önder KIZILKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 346
T-189	14:30-14:40	Anatomical and Palynological Characteristics of Taxa Papaver rhoeas L. and Papaver dubium L. subsp. laevigatum (M.Bieb.) Kadereit	Hasan ÖZESKİCİLER, Osman TUGAY and Deniz ULUKUŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 347

Session 2.11			12 JULY 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-190	14:00-14:10	Design and Assessment of the Solar Energy Based Direct Steam Generation Supercritical CO2 Brayton Cycle	Serpil ÇELİK TOKER, Önder KIZILKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 348
T-191	14:11-14:20	Efficient Computation of Exponential Matrices for Large Symmetric Negative Semidefinite Matrices	Gul Karaduman	Turkey	Submission 350
T-192	14:20-14:30	Symbol Detection with Deep Learning	Fatih Aslan and Yaşar Becerikli	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 354
T-193	14:30-14:40	Micro RNAs: The Game Changers of Diagnosis and Therapy of Human Cardiovascular Diseases	Habibe Karadaş, Hamid Ceylan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 355
T-194	14:40-14:50	Web Uygulama Zafiyetlerinin Keşfinde Açıklanabilir Yapay Zekânın Yeri	Erhan BAŞ, Ahmet Ali Süzen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 356
T-195	14:50-15:00	Erzincan İli'nin Depremselliği, Zemin Özelliklerinin Belirlenmesinin Önemi ve Gereklilikler	Fahriye Akar	Turkey	Submission 359
T-196	15:00-15:10	Kurumsal Ağlara Yapılan Saldırılarda Açıklanabilir Yapay Zekânın Yeri	Özer Yaz, Ahmet Ali Süzen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 360
T-197	15:10-15:20	Impact of Al2O3-Cu/Water Hybrid Nanofluid and Impinging Jet on Moving Plate at High Reynolds Numbers: A Numerical Study	Recep Ekiciler	Turkey	Submission 362
T-198	15:20-15:30	Development and Characterization of a Paper-Based Sensor for Colorimetric Urea Detection in Artificial Urine	Burak YAŞASIN and Mustafa ŞEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 363
T-199	15:30-15:40	Developing a Paper-Based Sensor for Cholesterol Measurement and Processing Images Using ImageJ	Saadet Demirbaş and Mustafa ŞEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 364

Session 2.12			12 JULY 2023 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-200	14:00-14:10	PHYSICAL EXAMPLES OF NONLINEAR DYNAMICAL SYSTEMS	Fatma Aydogmus and Eren Tosyali	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 366
T-201	14:11-14:20	Data Scientist Selection in IT Industry: SMCDM Approach	Emine Nur Nacar	Turkey	Submission 367
T-202	14:20-14:30	EĞİTİM YAPILARINDA DİKEY YEŞİL SİSTEM ENERJİ ANALİZ SİMÜLASYONU: ÇUKUROVA ÜNİVERSİTESİ	Ülkü ŞİMŞEK ŞENGÜL, Özlem ŞENYİĞİT SARIKAYA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 380
T-203	14:30-14:40	Developments in Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USVs): A Review	Semih Kale	Turkey	Submission 392
T-204	14:40-14:50	Geleneksel Makine Öğrenmesi ile Rakam Seslerinin Sınıflandırılması	M. Alptekin Engin, Latif Akçay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 394
T-205	14:50-15:00	Development of an Internet of Things Based Purified Water Quality Monitoring System	Mehmet Akif ÖZTÜRK, Ahmet Fırat YELKUVAN, Emre ÜNSAL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 397
T-206	15:00-15:10	Performance analysis of a novel solar assisted air source heat pump	Kutbay Sezen	Turkey	Submission 398
T-207	15:10-15:20	The Role of miRNAs in Asthma	Hilal Tosun, Hamid Ceylan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 402
T-208	15:20-15:30	Exploring Somali Sentiment Analysis: A Resource-Light Approach for Small-scale Text Classification	Kadar Bahar and Nehad T.A Ramaha	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 405
T-209	15:30-15:40	Artık Bağlantılar ile Düzenlenen U-Net Mimarisi Kullanarak Beyin Çıkarımı	Çağrı DAŞGIN, Kali GÜRKAHRAMAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 413

Session 2.13			12 JULY 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-210	15:00-15:10	ALÜMİNYUM MALZEMLERİ İMALATI SEKTÖRÜNÜN PERFORMANS DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ:TR8 BÖLGESİ VE TÜRKİYE GENELİ	Ali SEVİNÇ, Tamer EREN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 6
T-211	15:11-15:20	Machine Learning Based b-Shaped Monopole Antenna for RF Energy Harvesting Applications	Yunus Emre KUŞİN, Merih PALANDÖKEN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 7
T-212	15:20-15:30	Numerical study of InGaN/GaN heterojunction PIN based solar cell	Mourad Kaddeche, Zine Eddine Kaddeche	Turkey, Algeria	Submission 243
T-213	15:30-15:40	A physics-based analytical model of a gate field-plated AlGaIn/GaN High Electron Mobility Transistor	Mourad Kaddeche, Zine Eddine Kaddeche	Turkey, Algeria	Submission 245
T-214	15:40-15:50	P22 Çeliklerinin Sabit Basınç ve Farklı Sıcaklıklar Altında Sertlik ve Mikroyapısının İncelenmesi	Mehmet Akif AYIRT, Gökhan ARICI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 349
T-215	15:50-16:00	Performance Analysis of Large-scale Networks in Ns-2	Ahmet Zengin and İdris Cesur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 376
T-216	16:00-16:10	Gaz Türbinli Kombine Güç Çevrimlerinin Termodinamik Analizi	Rabi Karaali, Arzu Keven	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 385
T-217	16:10-16:20	Rekuperatörlü Kombine Güç Çevrimlerinin Optimum Çalışma Şartları ve Performans Analizi	Arzu Keven, Rabi Karaali	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 389
T-218	16:20-16:30	Human Sitting Postures Classification Based on Angular Features with Fuzzy-Logic Labeling	Huseyin COSKUN	Turkey	Submission 404
T-219	16:30-16:40	Investigation of the Change of Electric Energy Generation Sources in Turkey by Statistical Methods	Cengiz Gazeloğlu and Tunahan Turhan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 410

Session 2.14			12 JULY 2023 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-220	15:00-15:10	Stress Analysis of Belt Conveyor Roller Tube	Ayberk Düzenli, Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 433
T-221	15:11-15:20	Kamu Sektöründe Proje Yönetimi: Örnek Bir Uygulama	Beste Desticioğlu Taşdemir, Merve Tosya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 441
T-222	15:20-15:30	Spectral entropy complexity analysis of a 3D five-term chaotic system with cubic nonlinearity	Abdullah Gokyildirim	Turkey	Submission 442
T-223	15:30-15:40	Analysis of The Mechanical Properties of Inconel 718	Çağlar Korkmaz, Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 447
T-224	15:40-15:50	Analysis of Parameter Relationships Influencing Prostate Cancer using the Soft Set Model	Zehra Güzel Ergül, Naime Demirtaş and Orhan Dalkılıç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 451
T-225	15:50-16:00	Bicycle Frame Design And Structural Analysis	Kutluay İnce, Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 453
T-226	16:00-16:10	Design and Optimization of a Super Capacitor-Based High-Speed Charging System for Electric Vehicles	Semih SUBAŞI, Gürkan AYDEMİR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 454
T-227	16:10-16:20	Hybrid Desiccant Cooling Systems and Solar Assisted Methods	Kutbay Sezen	Turkey	Submission 455
T-228	16:20-16:30	Foaming the polyvinyl acetate (PVA) and poly urethane (PU) wood adhesive and characterization	Orhan Kelleci, Süheyla Esin Köksal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 461
T-229	16:30-16:40	Futbol Kulüplerinin Borçlarının Teverruk Yöntemi ile Yapılandırılmasının Finansal Açıdan İncelenmesi	Necati Alperen Tekeli, Emirhan Erdiñç, Gürkan Işık	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 463

Session 2.15			12 JULY 2023 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-230	16:00-16:10	L Tipinde Yapılan Yapıştırma Bağlantısında Partikül Etkisinin Belirlenmesi	Hüseyin DAMKAYA, Edip ÇETKİN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 464
T-231	16:11-16:20	Çiftçi ve Fabrika İş Birliği ile Sürdürülebilir Hasat Çizelgeleme	Bedirhan Sarımehmet, Mehmet Pınarbaşı, Hacı Mehmet Alakaş, Tamer Eren	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 468
T-232	16:20-16:30	Remodeling of the Drone Chassis Designed for Additive Manufacturing Method According to Topology Optimization	Alican YAKIN, Tuncay ŞİMŞEK and Adnan AKKURT	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 469
T-233	16:30-16:40	Doğal Afetlerde Arama Kurtarma Ekiplerinin Çizelgelenmesi: Aydın Depremi Senaryosu	Elif Akdaş, Tamer Eren	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 470
T-234	16:40-16:50	Vakum Tüp Güneş Kolektörlerinde Termal Performans İyileştirme Yöntemleri	Hakan DUMRUL, Edip TAŞKESEN, Fatih ARLI, Mustafa YENER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 471
T-235	16:50-17:00	Isı Değiştirici Temizleme Yöntemleri Ve Verimlilik	Edip TAŞKESEN, Hakan DUMRUL, Fatih ARLI	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 472
T-236	17:00-17:10	YAPI SEKTÖRÜNDE YENİLENEBİLİR ENERJİ KAYNAKLARININ KULLANIMI	Esin Işık, Buse Ün, Gülgün Mıstıkoğlu, Ercan Erdiş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 475
T-237	17:10-17:20	Recovery of Lead from Used Batteries through Electro-reduction	Kürşad Oğuz OSKAY	Turkey	Submission 476
T-238	17:20-17:30	ERP SİSTEMLERİ İLE DIŞ KAYNAKLAR ARASI ENTEGRASYONLAR İLE MALİYET OPTİMİZASYONU	Ali ULUDAĞ, Mehmet Onur OLGUN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 479
T-239	17:30-17:40	Kompozit Zırhların Geometrisinin Balistik Dayanıma Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Mehmet Orhan Şenaslan, İlyas İstif	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 480

Session 2.16			12 JULY 2023 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-240	16:00-16:10	Mega Projelerin Halka Arz Yöntemi ile Finansmanı Üzerine Bir İnceleme: Yavuz Sultan Selim Köprüsü ve Kuzey Marmara Otoyolu Örneği	Ramazan Gürbüz, Rıdvan Yalçın	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 481
T-241	16:11-16:20	Omurilik Felçli Fiziksel Engelli Bireylere Yönelik Giyilebilir Teknoloji Ürünlerdeki Sensörlerin Sahip Olması Gereken Özelliklerin Değerlendirilmesi	Emre Yazıcı, Mehmet Tan, Hacı Mehmet Alakaş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 483
T-242	16:20-16:30	Classification of Firearms with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks	Enes AYAN	Turkey	Submission 485
T-243	16:30-16:40	Synthesis and Optical Characterization of ZnO Nanorods	Selin Sarıtan, Hakan Colak, Feyza Oke-Altuntas and Halit Altuntas	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 489
T-244	16:40-16:50	COMPARISON OF ORBITAL AND MANUAL WELDING FOR MANUFACTURING STAINLESS STEEL HEAT EXCHANGER	Berfin Er, Taylan M. Daş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 497
T-245	16:50-17:00	ACİL DURUM VE AFETLERDE ALTERNATİF GÜZERGÂH SEÇİMİ: KIRIKKALE İLİNDE BİR UYGULAMA	Beyza Altın, Buket Özer, Emel Güven, Tamer Eren	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 498
T-246	17:00-17:10	DC Mikro Şebekelerde Sabit Güç Yükü Karşısında PI ve Geri Adım Kontrol Yöntemlerinin Gerilim Kontrol Performansı ve Karşılaştırması	Mustafa Güngör, Mehmet Emin Asker	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 500
T-247	17:10-17:20	Service Quality in Maritime Businesses: Bibliometric View	Ali Tehci, Yusuf Ersoy	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 502
T-248	17:20-17:30	Imaging of High-Intensity Therapeutic Ultrasound (HITU) in a Rabbit Model Inoculated with Glioblastoma Cells: Investigating the Effects on Carbonic Anhydrase IX Enzymes and Paraoxonase Enzyme Family	Kaan Tugberk Ozdemir, Ender Simsek, Giyas Ayberk	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 503
T-249	17:30-17:40	Overview of Hydrogen Production by Electrochemical Method; Advantages and Disadvantages	Ayşe Elif ATEŞ, Sinan ATEŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 506

Session 2.17			12 JULY 2023 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-250	17:00-17:10	Biological Hydrogen Production from Urban and Industrial Wastewater	Ayşe Elif ATEŞ, Sinan ATEŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 511
T-251	17:10-17:20	ASSESSING THE EFFICACY OF LSTM, TRANSFORMER, AND RNN ARCHITECTURES IN TEXT SUMMARIZATION	Seda BAYAT, Gultekin ISIK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 515
T-252	17:20-17:30	NTRU Anahtar Kapsülleme Mekanizması İçin Uygulamaya Özel İşlemci Tasarımı	Latif Akçay, Mustafa Alptekin Engin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 518
T-253	17:30-17:40	Çukur ve Tümsek Ayna Geometrisinde Emici Yüzeyle Sahip Güneş Hava Kolektörlerinin Sayısal Analizi	Murat ÖZTÜRK, Erdem ÇİFTÇİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 521
T-254	17:40-17:50	Sürdürülebilirlik Kapsamında Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri Çalışmalarının İncelenmesi	Mahmud Zahid Mutlu, M. Hanefi Calp	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 525
T-255	17:50-18:00	TARIMDA DRONE SEÇİMİ VE ÇİZELGELEMESİ: KIRIKKALE İLİ ÖRNEĞİ	Mehmet Batuhan Gürbüz, Yasin Erbaş, SerhatAda, Ervanur Karaşahin, Emel Güven, Tamer Eren	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 526
T-256	18:00-18:10	Numerical Comparison of Active Shielding Techniques for Magnetic Fluid Hyperthermia Application	Serhat Küçükdermenci	Turkey	Submission 528
T-257	18:10-18:20	Alıç Püresi ile Marinasyon ve Ultrason Uygulamasının Hindî Göğüs Etinin Fizikokimyasal, Teknolojik ve Tekstürel Özellikleri Üzerine Etkisi	Nuran ERDEM, Süleyman GÖKMEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 529
T-258	18:20-18:30	Office Seat Design And Analysis	Mehmet Berkay Yaltraklı, Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 530
T-259	18:30-18:40	Lupinus albus L. subsp. albus Takson Spesifik Genomik SSR Markörlerinin Geliştirilmesi	Yaren Bayram, İbrahim Çelik, Osman Tugay, Deniz Ulukuş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 545

Session 2.18			12 JULY 2023 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-260	17:00-17:10	A Study on Stability and Physicochemical Properties of Soybean Oil-in-Water Emulsions Prepared with Exudate Apple Gum	Mukaddes Karataş and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 548
T-261	17:10-17:20	Siyah Havuç Posasının Antimikrobiyal Aktivitesinin İncelenmesi	Tülay DURAN, Zuhâl SAHİN, Fatih SONMEZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 550
T-262	17:20-17:30	Two-Position Synthesis of the Four-Bar Planar Linkage Mechanisms Using Artificial Neural Networks	Onur Denizhan	Turkey	Submission 551
T-263	17:30-17:40	The Importance of Logistics 4.0 Within the Scope of Industry 4.0: Evaluation of Logistics 4.0 in An Enterprise in Terms of Sustainability	Ayşenur ERDİL	Turkey	Submission 562
T-264	17:40-17:50	Evaluating the Environmental Impacts and Sustainability of Gasoline-Ethanol Blends on Vehicle Exhaust Emissions	Beytullah Eren and Idris Cesur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 578
T-265	17:50-18:00	Didim Akbuk Bay (Aydın/Turkey) Dune Plant Diversity, Threatening Factors and Solution Proposals	Fadime Eryılmaz Pehlivan	Turkey	Submission 592
T-266	18:00-18:10	Performances of Pre-Trained Models in Classification of Body Cavity Fluid Cytology Images	Nadide Yücel, Muhammed Yildirim, Serpil Aslan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 443
T-267	18:10-18:20	Akıllı Lojistik Kapsamında Filyos Liman Projesinin Sürdürülebilir Kalkınmaya Etkileri	Sezin GÜLERYÜZ, Sedra ALAYOUB , Yıldız TEMEL, Oğuzhan DEMİRCİ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 415
T-268	18:20-18:30	DÜZCE İLİNDE BULUNAN BİR PROJE ANADOLU LİSESİ BİLİŞİM SINIFI İÇİN AHP TEKNİĞİYLE ALL IN ONE BİLGİSAYAR SEÇİMİ	Sezin GÜLERYÜZ, Hatice KULABAŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 419
T-269	18:30-18:40	Makine ve Ekipman Seçim Kriterleri İçerisinde Dizel Jeneratör Setlerinin AHP Yaklaşımı ile Sınıflandırılması	Sezin GÜLERYÜZ, Adem KOCABAŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 425

Session 2.19			12 JULY 2023 18:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-270	18:00-18:10	Gamma-ray shielding properties of amorphous alloys with various tantalum concentrations	M. Tokaç, Z. Y. Khattari and M. S. Al-Buriahi	Turkey, Jordan, Turkey	Submission 495
T-271	18:10-18:20	Açıklanabilir Yapay Zeka Teknikleri İle Parkinson Hastalık Teşhisi	Tuğçe KAÇAR, Mehmet Onur OLGUN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 496
T-272	18:20-18:30	Biomedical signal processing methods for neuromarketing: A comparative study	Suzan SABAN, Eda DAĞDEVİR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 532
T-273	18:30-18:40	The Effect of Substrate Rotation Speed on the Optical Characteristics of Gallium Oxides Grown by Spin-Coating Technique	Halit Altuntas and Enis Sert	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 542
T-274	18:40-18:50	The effect of fluorine doping on the improvement of optical properties of lithium oxide	Nilüfer ERTEKİN	Turkey	Submission 544
T-275	18:50-19:00	OFİS ERGONOMİSİNDE İŞYERİ MOBİLYA TASARIMI	Gül Uslu, Ergün ERASLAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 549
T-276	19:00-19:10	Makine Seçiminde Sezgisel Bulanık TOPSIS Yönteminin Kullanılması ve Bir Uygulama	Buse Duygu DAĞIDIR, Barış ÖZKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 552
T-277	19:10-19:20	Research on Pollination Biomorphology of Malvaceae by <i>Bombus terrestris</i> L. 1758 (Insecta:Hymenoptera)	Aysel Kekillioğlu, Ebru Kunduracı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 553
T-278	19:20-19:30	Embryological Development Processes in Insects (Arthropoda: Insecta)	Aysel Kekillioğlu, Buse Yıldız	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 554
T-279	19:30-19:40	Pollinator Hymenoptera (Arthropoda:Insecta)	Aysel Kekillioğlu, Ömer Eren Bostan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 555

Session 2.20			12 JULY 2023 18:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-280	18:00-18:10	GRAFEN OKSİT TEMELLİ NANOKOMPOZİTLERİN BİYOSENSÖR PLATFORMU OLARAK KULLANIMLARI	Başak BÜYÜK, Sema DEMİRCİ UZUN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 564
T-281	18:10-18:20	Kayseri İli Nohut Ekim Alanlarında Nohut Yaprak sineği [<i>Liriomyza Cicerina Rondani</i> (Diptera: Agromyzidae)]'nin Yaygınlığı, Bulaşıklık Oranı ve Popülasyon Dalgalanması	Ahmet ÖZKAN, Murat MUŞTU	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 570
T-282	18:20-18:30	Comparison of Machinability Performances in Milling of Al-7Si-Mg and Al-7Si-0.6Mg Alloys	Cem ALPARSLAN, Şenol BAYRAKTAR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 571
T-283	18:30-18:40	Weight Reduction of Spars on the Wing of a Fixed-Wing UAV	İsmail Okan Keskinkaya and Mehmet Sunar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 575
T-284	18:40-18:50	Silis Dumanı Kullanımının Kolemanit ve Kolemanit Atığı İçeren Harç Karışımların Dayanımına Etkisi	Süleyman Özen, Muhammet Gökhan Altun, Muhammed Yasin Durgun, Musa Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 579
T-285	18:50-19:00	İnsan-Bilgisayar Etkileşimi Kapsamında E-Devlet Web Sayfası Kullanılabilirlik Analizi	Hatice KULABAŞ, Ümmühan AVCI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 585
T-286	19:00-19:10	İnsan-Bilgisayar Etkileşimi ve Kullanılabilirlik: Navigasyon Arayüz İncelemesi	Kübra Yasa, Ümmühan Avcı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 586
T-287	19:10-19:20	Population parameters of the Horse Mackerel (<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>) in the Southeastern Black Sea during 2019-2020 fishing season	Tuncay Yeşilçiçek	Turkey	Submission 587
T-288	19:20-19:30	Biyokütle Atığından Üretilen Aktifleştirilmiş Karbon: Süperkapasitörler İçin Enerji Depolama Malzemesi	Salim Erol	Turkey	Submission 588
T-289	19:30-19:40	YouTube Mobil Uygulaması Kullanılabilirlik Analizi	Elif ÇALIŞKAN, Ümmühan AVCI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 589

Session 2.21			12 JULY 2023 19:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-290	19:00-19:10	Dynamic and Static Analysis of Deep Excavation of Poligon Station in İzmir Metro Line	Ender Başarı, Yeşim Tuskan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 593
T-291	19:10-19:20	Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Character of Metamorphic-hosted Bauxite Mineralization in Eastern Taurus Orogenic Belt	Cihan Yalçın, Hatice Kara, Mehmet Ali Ertürk and Abdullah Sar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 602
T-292	19:20-19:30	A Comparative Analysis of Green Taxes In OECD Countries	Özgür Utku MACUNLUOĞLU	Turkey	Submission 604
T-293	19:30-19:40	The effects of ripe and unripe banana flours originated from bananas grown in Mersin on Muffin Cakes	Nazlı Begüm Kansu, Sedat Sayar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 427
T-294	19:40-19:50	Rüzgâr Enerjisinin Tarihsel Gelişimi	Ömer Kılıçoğlu, Mustafa Arif Özgür	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 428
T-295	19:50-20:00	Mudurnu Çayı Havzasında Yağış ve Sıcaklık Verilerinin Trend Analizi	Gamze Tuncer, Osman Sönmez	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 429
T-296	20:00-20:10	Seismic Strengthening of Stone Barrel Vault Structures by Foam Concrete	Furkan Günday	Turkey	Submission 535
T-297	20:10-20:20	Investigation of GRC Retrofitting Effect on Masonry Dome Using FEM	Furkan Günday	Turkey	Submission 536
T-298	20:20-20:30	Analytical Study on Retrofitting Concrete Retaining Wall with Concrete Lining	Sertaç Tuhta	Turkey	Submission 537
T-299	20:30-20:40	Simulation of Shotcrete in RC Tunnel Using Finite Element Method	Sertaç Tuhta	Turkey	Submission 538

Session 2.22			12 JULY 2023 19:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-300	19:00-19:10	ZEMİN İYİLEŞTİRME UYGULAMASININ DİNAMİK ZEMİN TEPKİ ANALİZ SONUÇLARINA ETKİSİ	Mesut Aslan, Ender Başarı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 584
T-301	19:10-19:20	Creating Large Language Model Applications Utilizing LangChain: A Primer on Developing LLM Apps Fast	Oguzhan Topsakal and Tahir Cetin Akinci	USA, USA	Submission 591
T-302	19:20-19:30	New Design of Miniaturized Tri-teeth Metamaterial Resonator for Satellite Applications	Berka Mohammed, Umut Özkaya, Baghdad Bey Abdelkader	Algeria, Turkey, Algeria	Submission 598
T-303	19:30-19:40	Tekstil Sektöründe Süreç İyileştirme İçin Ürün Hatalarının Analizi	Büşra BAKDAAL, Esra Kurt TEKEZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 610
T-304	19:40-19:50	Investigation of Different Types of Parabolic Trough Solar Collector Designs	S.C. Ulucan and O. Özsolak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 612
T-305	19:50-20:00	PANDEMİ DÖNEMİNDE HASTA BAKIMINDA GİYİLEBİLİR TEKNOLOJİLERİN KULLANIMI VE HASTA BAKIMI UZAKTAN EĞİTİM PROGRAMLARI İÇİN GELECEKTEKİ UYGULAMA ALANLARI	Saliha Bekmezci, Serap Uğur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 534
T-306	20:00-20:10	Investigation of The Corrosion Properties of Alloys Manufactured By Additive Manufacturing Method	Fatma Nazlı ÖZSOLAK	Turkey	Submission 611
T-307	20:10-20:20	İtfaiye İstasyonu Yer Seçiminde F-Fucom Yöntemi İle Kriterlerin Sıralanması	Gül USLU, Babek ERDEBİLLİ	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 21
T-308	20:20-20:30	Framework for Localization of Forgery Regions in Image	Canberk Şahin, Mustafa Özden	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 609
T-309	20:30-20:40	Yapay Zeka Desteği İle Televizyon Kontrolü	Esra ERGİN, Umut ÖZKAYA	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 23
T-310	20:40-20:50	Investigation Of The Effect Of Microwave-Assisted Freeze-Drying Method On Quality Properties Of Strawberry	Zehra DURAK, T. Koray PALAZOĞLU, Welat MİRAN, Mahir CİN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 257